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D5.1 - Plan for dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities (DECP)

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
COMMS	Communication
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DEM	Direct Email Marketing
EAG	External Advisory Board
EU	European
F2F	Face to Face
KER	Key Exploitable Result
NEB	New European Bauhaus
PPC	Pay-Per-Click
PR	Press Release
R&I	Research and Innovation
SDO	Standard Development Organisation
SEC	Section
SG	Stakeholder Group
TWG	Thematic Working Group
UTM	Urchin Tracking Module
WP	Work Package

Keywords

New European Bauhaus; Communication; Dissemination; Exploitation.

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Executive summary

This first digiNEB.eu Plan for dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities report sets out the strategy for the lifetime of the project in terms of communicating its goals, outputs and impacts, describing how it is sharing its results and building a community.

In terms of planning, it defines specific actions and measures for all activities related to community building and practical assets that are key to ensuring the proper visibility of digiNEB.eu as enabler of the digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus aimed at underpinning the project's exploitation and sustainability path. The report also outlines the digiNEB.eu stakeholder groups, their value propositions and targeted engagement activities with dedicated communication and dissemination campaigns. The deliverable also provides a concise report on current achievements and established synergies.

The report concludes by showing how the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities will be monitored through pre-defined KPIs coupled with qualitative assessments.

The Plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication is designed as a coordinated, joint effort by all partners. Every partner will contribute to the actions foreseen in the communication plan, in proportion to effort assigned, knowledge and skills. It is the first such report with the next versions coming in September 2024, which will update the activities performed in terms of dissemination and communication and increasingly focus on the exploitation and sustainability strategy of the digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus.

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1. Introduction and structure of the document

1.1 Scope

This deliverable is the first version of the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication activities. The aim of this document is to define the strategy and foreseen initiatives for communication and dissemination activities, through dedicated multichannel actions and campaigns that help the project team engage with dedicated stakeholder groups.

The deliverable also showcases an exploitation strategy, detailing both joint and individual activities that each partner will perform to valorise in the longer term the results and assets generated by the project.

A second and final release of the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities performed is going to be produced in M24.

1.2 Structure of this document

The document is structured into six main sections that aim to provide a comprehensive overview of the communication, dissemination, exploitation strategies and plans employed by the project:

- **Section 2** outlines the project's communication and dissemination strategy, which is targeted towards specific Stakeholder Groups (SGs). This section also describes the various campaigns that have been implemented to achieve the communication and dissemination goals.
- **Section 3** presents a revised value proposition for each SG and assesses the overall effectiveness of each Asset for the targeted SG.
- **Section 4** showcases the Communication and Dissemination plan, highlighting the channels and elements used to achieve the plan. It also discusses the role of multipliers and synergies in achieving the communication and dissemination objectives.
- **Section 5** provides insights into the initial individual and joint exploitation plans and offers an overview of the digiNEB.eu Roadmap.
- **Section 6** discusses the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that have been implemented to monitor the quantitative impact of the communication and dissemination strategies.
- **Section 7:** draws the conclusions and summarises the next steps.

This basic structure will be maintained for possible further iterations of this document.

1.3 Relation with other project deliverables

The following deliverables of digiNEB.eu are related to this document:

- D1.1 “Project Handbook” (V1.0 published in December 2022) as this deliverable presents the main project management aspects of digiNEB.eu and details procedures which have been followed to produce the present deliverable.
- D4.1 “Stakeholder engagement plan and adoption & monitoring report - initial version” as this document showcases the engagement objectives, target stakeholder groups and main engagement channels for its community.
- D5.2 “Preliminary version of the digiNEB.eu Deployment Roadmap” (expected to be published in M12, i.e. August 2023) as the development of the Roadmap will contribute to the definition of the sustainability path to put into practice the exploitation aspects.

2. Dissemination & communication strategy

The digiNEB.eu project is fully aligned with the strategic objectives and priorities of the EU Industrial Strategy and the Green Deal, aimed at creating a new transition pathway for the proximity and social economy ecosystem. This transformation can only take place through the creation of a twin green and digital transition when different stakeholders collaborate to create bridges between the different scales of the built environment. digiNEB.eu creates exactly such an EU network and platform for the involved ecosystem, including SMEs and large industrial players, engaging with public actors and civil society stakeholders to foster wide adoption of digital solutions and lead specific follow-up actions and commitments. Specifically, the project will prepare the NEB community to support and engage with the Digital Europe Programme and European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIH), to increase adoption of EC- and national-funded digital solutions, capacities for R&I and skills development for digital innovation and uptake.

In this context, effective communication and dissemination is a crucial component for the project's success. This deliverable outlines the strategy and tactics employed to promote the digiNEB.eu main goals, support stakeholder engagement, and ensure that the project's findings and outcomes reach a wide audience during the project's lifetime. By leveraging various communication channels and employing a targeted approach, the strategy leads to an actionable plan (Sec. 4 of this document) that maximises the impact of digiNEB.eu, while driving positive change.

Even though this plan is delivered after just a semester of activities of digiNEB.eu, relevant dissemination and communication activities have already been designed and implemented in agreement with the strategy described in this section, and examples of early results achieved so far are enclosed.

Overall, the communication and dissemination plan builds on a multi-faceted strategy, with a pan-European breadth, and founded on the following elements, further described below:

1. Disseminating the project's main **assets**;
2. A focused approach to the target different **stakeholder groups (SGs)**;
3. **User-centred** value propositions & motivational mechanisms;
4. Continuous cooperation with the **NEB** Communication team.

Overall, the **content produced by the other activities of the workplan**, namely Task 2.2 "Thematic Working Groups (TWGs)", Task 2.3 "Catalogue of NEB digital projects & solutions", Task 3.1 "Training platform", Task 3.2 "Transferring innovation best practices", Task 4.1 "Stakeholder engagement", Task 4.2 "NEB synergies", Task 5.2 "Events management", will fuel the DECP, providing the necessary ground for interest to be built and the communication and dissemination messages to be effective.

2.1. Disseminating the project's main assets

A brief description of the digiNEB.eu's five main assets is provided below. The Assets are weaved into the communication and dissemination plan, as further described in Sec. 4.

Asset#1: NEB Toolkit: Inaugurated during M01, this asset aims to support our stakeholders (see Deliverable D4.1 "Stakeholder engagement plan and adoption & monitoring report - initial version" /3/ and Sec. 3 of this document, below) in the promotion of their digital solutions through the NEB channels as well as the adoption of new solutions. As a result, it's the object of targeted campaigns aimed to ensure that these resources are effectively disseminated and promoted throughout the project lifetime. Specific actions included communication campaigns that leveraged a variety of channels, including social media, email marketing, website banners, and targeted ads. These were designed to reach a broad audience and generate interest in the project, as well as to promote the digital toolkit and observatory to those who would benefit from them the most. In addition to our

multichannel campaign, an individual engagement plan was implemented, consisting of targeted emails to specific stakeholders chosen as potential digital solutions creators (see Sec. 4.2 “Campaigns”).

Asset#2: NEB Observatory: Inaugurated during M03, this asset aims to support our stakeholders connecting with each other by providing a space to map and monitor NEB-related initiatives bridging the gap with the digital world. As a result, it was the object of targeted campaigns aimed to ensure that these resources were effectively disseminated and promoted. Specific actions included multichannel communication campaigns that leveraged a variety of channels, including social media, email marketing, website banners, and targeted ads. in the project and could benefit from our resources. These emails were personalised and tailored to the specific needs and interests of each stakeholder, which allowed the digiNEB.eu consortium to engage with them on a more personal level and build stronger relationships. Through these targeted communications, it was possible to increase awareness of our project, drive traffic to our digital toolkit and observatory, and build a strong community of engaged users who will support our work in the following months.

Asset#3: eLearning Platform: This platform, launched in April 2023, will provide training programmes and material targeting specific stakeholder groups such as national and regional authorities. A targeted multichannel campaign will ensure effective dissemination and promotion of its main assets, showcasing the topics of e-learning materials made accessible via the platform via infographic and digiNEB.eu branded storytelling elements, and tailored to the identified stakeholder groups. Training activities organised by projects included in the Observatory and providers in the Toolkit will also be disseminated here.

Asset#4: Thematic Working Groups (TWGs): The digiNEB.eu initiative will set up Thematic Working Groups (TWGs) with top experts, researchers, and stakeholders to address priority topics. A series of 16 workshops will be carried out to validate TWG content and create best practices, gap analysis reports, and policy recommendations to be shared widely with the NEB digital ecosystem and towards the European Commission. Multichannel campaigns and targeted efforts will be established to effectively share the TWGs' progress. Moreover, a network campaign will showcase the reports of the 4 Technical Working Groups on: Design & Architecture, Production & Construction, Verticals, Community & Sustainability and the digiNEB.eu. In addition, a human-interest series on the digiNEB.eu Early Adopters, sharing their success stories via posts with pictures and quotes. Finally, a visual Roadmap tailored to community needs will be crafted.

Asset#5: Early Adopters Programme: To promote the digiNEB.eu Early Adopters, a communication and Early Adopters campaign will be launched with the aim to identify the target audience, develop a clear message about the benefits of becoming an Early Adopter, utilise a multi-channel promotional approach (e.g. social media, email newsletters, and webinars), provide incentives and rewards to encourage participation, highlight success stories and best practices of current Early Adopters.

2.2. A focused approach to the target different stakeholder groups (SGs)

To ensure digiNEB.eu project has a meaningful impact and reaches its target audience, a focused approach to engaging with different stakeholder groups (SGs) is employed, drawing from seven identified target groups, as described in D4.1 “Stakeholder engagement plan and adoption & monitoring report - initial version” and further detailed in Sec. 3.

2.3. User-centred value propositions & motivational mechanisms

As relevant stakeholders are continuously engaged in communication and marketing activities, user-centred value propositions and motivational mechanisms are essential for engaging different stakeholder groups, offering them incentives to contribute to the project’s main goals. For instance,

visibility provided by digiNEB.eu to Early Adopters will support their personal pan-European stature and will eventually lead to further career opportunities for them. Furthermore, contributors to the TWGs are also receiving a positive visibility for them as they will establish themselves as key content providers in the NEB field and they will also be mentioned in the landscape and gap analysis reports.

2.4. Continuous cooperation with the NEB Communication team

From its inception, digiNEB.eu has forged a strategic collaboration with the New European Bauhaus communication team to align its communication activities with the overarching strategy of NEB. The primary objective of this cooperation is to ensure that digiNEB.eu's communication efforts bolster the wider NEB movement. Specifically, the digiNEB.eu project seeks to advance the adoption of digital solutions to promote sustainability, beauty, and inclusivity in living spaces, which are fundamental pillars of the New European Bauhaus initiative.

2.5. Diversification of dissemination and communications across SGs

As stated in deliverable D4.1 “Stakeholder engagement plan and adoption & monitoring report - initial version” the dissemination and communication strategy is founded on a set of Stakeholder Groups (SGs, see the figure below), that will eventually be adapted according to the response from the field obtained in the stakeholder engagement activities – this will in turn be reflected in related adaptations to this strategy. Details on the value propositions, messaging and assets for each SG are presented in Sec. 3.

Figure 1 - Stakeholder Groups targeted by digiNEB.eu

This approach helped to strategically tailor social media communication to each group's specific needs and interests, and enabled the digiNEB.eu's consortium to engage with them in a more meaningful way. Leveraging digiNEB.eu's partners strong networks in both the international digital arena and the NEB ecosystem, SGs were engaged through customised and targeted campaigns since the project's very beginning. Engagement strategies included invitations to digiNEB.eu's events of interest, as well as mapping and monitoring their presence on the project's social media channels, which allowed us to better understand their preferences and tailor the project's messaging accordingly.

User-centred value proposition served the purpose to explain the benefits and value of digiNEB.eu assets to potential end users. The promotion of digital solutions aimed at promoting the NEB values of sustainability, inclusion and beauty simultaneously target different stakeholder groups providing inputs for innovative and sustainable designs as well as achieving environmental and social policy goals, business opportunities, and bottom-up social inclusion strategies. Similarly, motivational mechanisms provided incentives, rewards, and recognition for engaged stakeholders. Examples include access to training and professional development programs, public recognition, as well as product and services showcasing. All these motivational mechanisms were tailored to the needs and interests of different stakeholder groups, fostering a sense of ownership and buy-in to the project, thus motivating stakeholders to engage in meaningful ways.

In addition, the project team developed and is going to create effective marketing materials as they represent an important part of any communication and dissemination plan. Therefore, they can help ensure that the project's message is seen, understood, and remembered by your target audience. Since digiNEB.eu's inception, marketing materials constituted the backbone of the overall Communication and Dissemination plan. They particularly served the purpose to convey a clear message, tailored to the needs and expectations of each target SG.

- **Architects, Designers, Engineers (SG1):** effective marketing materials benefitted SG1 by showcasing new technologies, design trends, and innovative solutions in the field. Marketing materials included success stories and digital solutions demonstrating the practical application of new technologies, design principles, and engineering solutions.
- **Industry Players (SG2):** effective marketing materials benefitted SG2 promoting solutions and services potentially improving efficiency, reducing costs, and increasing profitability. In particular, success stories' spec sheets served the purpose to demonstrate the practical benefits of new technologies and fuelled awareness and interest in new products and services.
- **Research and Academia (SG3):** effective marketing materials benefitted SG3 by disseminating research findings and academic insights to a wider audience. In particular, post-webinar reports and slides fostered digiNEB.eu's reputation and visibility building, while also increasing the impact and relevance of the sponsored solutions.
- **Digital Technology Companies (SG4):** effective marketing materials benefitted SG4 by promoting the project's sponsored digital solutions to potential users and customers. In particular, marketing materials such as explainer videos promoted on digiNEB.eu's social media channels helped educate potential users about the benefits and features of new digital technologies.
- **Policy Makers (SG5):** effective marketing materials benefitted SG5 by promoting policy proposals and initiatives to key decision-makers and stakeholders involved in the project's events. Envisioned materials such as policy briefs and gap analysis papers resulting from thematic working groups discussions could help to build support for specific policy proposals, while also educating the public and other stakeholders about key policy issues.
- **National & Regional Authorities (SG6):** effective marketing materials benefitted SG6 by showcasing success stories linked to digital solutions that improved the quality of life for citizens. Community engagement materials used by digiNEB.eu encouraged civic investment and supported cultural initiatives, while also building trust and credibility with citizens and other stakeholders.
- **Civil Society Organizations and Citizens (SG7):** effective marketing materials benefitted SG7 by promoting NEB three core values of inclusivity, beauty and sustainability among citizen groups. These included relevant social media content educating the public about key issues, while also inspiring and empowering citizens to get involved and make a difference.

2.6. A Campaign based approach

The dissemination and communication strategy is built upon 6 campaigns that run throughout the entire project's lifetime. The campaigns help increase visibility of the project's results, support its sustainability plan, and engage with the SGs. Furthermore, they help ensure that the project's goals and objectives are aligned with the overarching goal of increasing the adoption of digital tools for the New European Bauhaus.

- **Campaign 1 (Branding, Project Communication and Awareness):** the aim of this campaign is to establish the digiNEB.eu identity and presence in the New European Bauhaus environment. The campaign started at the launch of the project and it will progress until September 2023. The main activities connected to it are:
 - Branding

- Launch of the website
- Set up of social media channels
- Development of graphic materials
- Launch of PPC campaigns
- Video interviews and promotion
- Preparation of newspieces, articles and PRs
- **Campaign 2 (Showcasing and sharing digital solutions for NEB):** this campaign aims to showcase the innovation brought by digital solutions for the New European Bauhaus, from both technological and social viewpoints. The campaign was launched in October 2023 and is going to end in September 2024. The main activities connected to this campaign are:
 - Launch of the NEB Digital Toolkit
 - Launch of the NEB Observatory
 - Launch of the TWG Discussion Forum
 - Launch of the eLearning Platform
 - Continuous mapping of digital solutions and eLearning courses
- **Campaign 3 (Recruitment to webinars, workshops, annual and 3rd-party events):** the aim of this campaign is to recruit new adopters of digital solutions for NEB through their engagement and participation to 3rd-party events or the digiNEB.eu webinars, workshops or annual events. The campaign runs 24 months, from October 2022 to September 2024. The main activities connected to Campaign nr. 3 are:
 - Organisation of 8 webinars
 - Organisation of 16 workshops
 - Organisation of 2 annual events
 - Participation to 3rd-party events
- **Campaign 4 (Early Adopters engagement):** the aim of this campaign is to recruit Early Adopters, who act as ambassadors of digiNEB.eu, and as a consequence, promote the adoption of digitalisation in NEB environments. The campaign started at M06 and runs until M18. The main activities that drive it are:
 - Set up of a registration form to apply to become and Early Adopter on the digiNEB.eu website
 - Promotion of the main achievements through a PR
 - Publication of Early Adopters success stories
- **Campaign 5 (Policy Recommendations):** The campaign aims to deliver influential recommendations to policy makers with dedicated policy briefs, landscape and gap analysis, and a strategic Roadmap to influence future work programmes in the NEB and digital environments. The main activities connected to this campaign are:
 - Publication of landscape and gap analysis reports
 - Publication of the digiNEB.eu Roadmap
- **Campaign 6 (Support to exploitation and sustainability):** This campaign aims to communicate the main impact gathered through the exploitation activities of the project. The main activities connected to it are:
 - Publication of a white paper in collaboration with the TWGs
 - Organisation of annual events to showcase the main results of the landscape and gap analysis and the Roadmap

2.7. Multichannel actions

digiNEB.eu uses various communication channels leveraging the project partners network and aims to produce a set of tailored communication formats targeting different stakeholder groups. The digiNEB.eu consortium can count on extensive expertise and experience in creating communication and dissemination strategies through actions to reach out to a broad range of stakeholders, media,

professional and social channels. Therefore, the **multichannel approach** followed by digiNEB.eu focuses on a variety of tools and initiatives that help foster community-building and engagement, as presented as a coordinated action in Table 1.

CHANNELS	IMPACT
Website	The collaborative Drupal based website is the public hub of the project with all results disseminated there. It hosts the NEB Digital Toolkit, NEB Observatory, the eLearning platform and online events
Social media	Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram and YouTube are harnessed to drive relevant, high intent traffic to the project’s website. Posts will be made using relevant hashtags and UTMs (Urchin Tracking Modules) created specifically for each post and channel to track site traffic. The UTM parameters included in a URL serve to identify the marketing campaign responsible for driving traffic to a particular website. Additionally, they assign the website session of the browser, as well as any subsequent sessions within the campaign attribution window, to that campaign.
Email	A branded newsletter service, which with its regular issues will become a solid channel that digiNEB.eu will leverage, to increase the community of experts, across industries and NEB-related topics
Workshops	16 workshops will be delivered to disseminate NEB digital solutions, facilitate a multi-stakeholder dialogue and ultimately close the gap between research and industry. The workshop series will be formatted as “hands-on prototyping workshops” (that create impacts at a degree of magnitude higher than ordinary workshops), zooming in on the value creation coming from NEB digital solutions, facilitating clustering and convergence on common themes and challenges, fostering the exchange of good practices, and identifying how digital transformation can contribute to the implementation of the new European Bauhaus Initiative
Webinars	8 webinars will take place during the project to identify commonly perceived barriers and to discuss how different R&I projects are addressing them. The webinars will form a core aspect identifying how current activities can shape road-mapping and policy recommendations
3rd-party events	Participation at 3rd-party events serves to showcase the project’s main results to people outside the consortium and external players
PPC	Pay-Per-Click Campaigns have the objective to broaden stakeholder reach, and increase subscribers, especially to the service-oriented items of the project (NEB Digital Toolkit, NEB Observatory, eLearning platform)

Table 1 - Multichannel actions and impact

3. Value propositions & communications to Stakeholder Groups

digiNEB.eu engages with seven Stakeholder Groups (SGs), whose main characteristics have been already presented in D4.1 “Stakeholder engagement plan and adoption & monitoring report – initial version”. As already presented in that deliverable, the SGs have been selected to bring their perspective, expertise, and skills to the project. The digiNEB.eu community will be engaged not only by addressing each of the 7 distinct Stakeholder Groups (SGs) with the most appropriate value proposition for such a group but also through a mission-driven, thematic approach that bridges sectors, ensures interdisciplinarity and allows for self-selection by interest rather than simply targeting specific industries and professions."

The SGs have been identified also to create a comprehensive network that can facilitate the connection between the digital ecosystem and the New European Bauhaus ones. While details about the Engagement Plan for each SG are presented in D4.1, this chapter focuses on the value propositions used to attract the SGs, the messaging conveyed through the communication activities and the assessment of the overall effectiveness of each asset encourage the adoption and exploitation of the project results by each SG.

3.1. SG#1 Architects, Designers, Engineers

This SG includes architects, designers, engineers and other professionals belonging to the NEB community and will be attracted and engaged with a specific value proposition and activities. This SG strives for effective and efficient applications and solutions that can allow performing their work in a more efficient, sustainable and inclusive manner. While this SG is aware of the needs, gaps and requirements for the implementation of NEB principles, they may still experience **challenges** related to lack of or incomplete knowledge about the digital solutions available for them and the benefits brought by the digital world to the NEB ecosystem.

The **benefits** brought by digiNEB.eu to this SG include a deeper comprehension of the possibilities of digitalization in terms of practical solutions, use cases, and application areas. Additionally, it provides an opportunity for the SG's needs and opinions to be heard by digital solutions providers and taken into account during the development and delivery of further solutions.

The **main message** to express their specific value proposition would be:

“Discover how digital solutions can improve your professional activities and make them adhere to the NEB principles, showcase the digital solutions and innovative technologies that you are already adopting and support the identification of needs, gaps and requirements for the implementation of the NEB initiative entering a co-creation space with dedicated working groups focused on analysing key trends in architecture and design”

The overall effectiveness of each Asset for this specific SG is indicated in the table, as a result of four elements of appeal, that will therefore have to be communicated with the needed effectiveness.

For each asset, an indicative measure spanning from 1 (lowest appeal) to 10 (highest appeal) has been added to the Table below.

SG#1 Appeal → Asset ↓	Relevance of the proposition	Direct advantage (what's in it for me?)	Uniqueness	Ease of exploitation	Overall effectiveness (on a scale 1 to 10, average of the 4 indicators)
Digital Toolkit	10- All SG#1 professionals can access the toolkit	7- Discover useful solutions for their professional	6 - Medium, the toolkit collects existing tools and	7- Most solutions are freely available, but may require	7.5

SG#1 Appeal → Asset ↓	Relevance of the proposition	Direct advantage (what's in it for me?)	Uniqueness	Ease of exploitation	Overall effectiveness (on a scale 1 to 10, average of the 4 indicators)
	or contribute to its population	activities	solutions	some training (based on the SG experience) or licences (depending on IPR) to be fully exploited	
Observatory	10 - All SG#1 professionals can access the Observatory or contribute to its population	8 - Keep up-to-date with latest information and success stories demonstrating digital applications for NEB community	8 - High - there is a lack of common European space that include best practices and success stories to adopt digital solutions for NEB	6- Success stories and best practices can be of inspiration but not always easy to replicate	8
Elearning catalogue	7- Attractiveness of the e-learning offer depends on each professional's skills and background	9- learning opportunities, getting recognition via certification, upskilling, visibility if involved as speakers to show best practices	7 - Medium-high (both courses from existing capacity building material and newly developed)	10 - hands-on engaging courses, learning material is provided to all trainees	8.25
Thematic Working Groups (TWGs)	7- selected members of SG#1 with proven experience can join the TWG workshops but all can contribute to suggest online discussion topics in line with the theme of each WG	8- it provides: -SG#1 visibility, if contributor to TWGs outputs, - access to state of the art mapping, - access to landscape analysis, -help identify needs and gaps for NEB's digitalisation, -information of latest trends	6 - Medium - the local living spaces environments have experts involved in working groups (e.g. European Construction Sector Observatory, living-in.eu working groups). However, the digiNEB.eu TWG are designed for SG#1 members to provide insights specifically connected to NEB	7- TWG outcomes will feed recommendations report and policy briefs, which may take time to be actually implemented	7
Early Adopters (EAs) network	10 - All SG#1 professionals can become EAs	7 - By becoming EAs, all SG#1 can receive visibility and promote how digitalisation has positively affected their work	9 - High - the Early Adopters network follow the principles of engagement envisioned by the NEB Champions network	5 - Complex and depending on notoriety of NEB at local level	7.75
Roadmap	7 - selected members of SG#1 with strong experience and understanding of NEB world will contribute to	7 - visibility if contributor to roadmapping, understanding of priorities, strategic insights	9 - High - the Roadmap can provide innovative insights and timings on how to increase the adoption of digital	6- Implementation connected to policy context complexity and uncertainty may arise due to the long-term nature of the	7.25

SG#1 Appeal → Asset ↓	Relevance of the proposition	Direct advantage (what's in it for me?)	Uniqueness	Ease of exploitation	Overall effectiveness (on a scale 1 to 10, average of the 4 indicators)
	roadmap, but wider number of members can provide feedback and suggestions		solutions	roadmap	

Table 2 - Articulation of the value proposition for SG#1

3.2. SG#2 Construction industry suppliers & other relevant industry players, including SDOs

This SG includes Construction industry suppliers and other relevant industry players such as start-ups, SMEs, associations in the building, mobility & health sectors, and SDOs. This SG interacts with SG1 and can play a role in the NEB arena. However, this SG could experience **challenges** related to lack of or incomplete knowledge about how they could contribute to NEB and foster innovation in this field.

The **benefits** brought by digiNEB.eu to this SG include a better understanding of digitalisation potentialities in terms of concrete solutions, as well as the possibility for their needs and voices to meet key players across various sectors with whom to create synergies and partnerships.

The **main message** to express their specific value proposition would be:

“Identify a common ground with the actors along the whole value chain of your industry and understand how to contribute to the definition of a wide range of innovative digital services and solutions to foster NEB-related innovation. Learn about the impact of digitalisation and NEB in your industry. Gain a simplified access and connections to digital solution providers and innovators to create partnerships and boost your competitiveness ”

The overall effectiveness of each Asset for this specific SG is indicated in the table below. As for the previous SG, for each asset an indicative measure spanning from 1 (lowest appeal) to 10 (highest appeal) has been added to the Table below.

SG#2 Appeal → Asset ↓	Relevance of the proposition	Direct advantage (what's in it for me?)	Uniqueness	Ease of exploitation	Overall effectiveness (on a scale 1 to 10, average of the 4 indicators)
Digital Toolkit	10- All SG#2 members can access the toolkit or contribute to its population	8- Discover useful solutions for your activity, enlarge your network connecting with digital solution providers	6 - Medium, the toolkit collects existing tools and solutions	7- Most solutions are freely available, but may require some trainings (based on the SG experience) or licences (depending on IPR) to be fully exploited	7.75
Observatory	10 - All SG#2 professionals can access the Observatory or contribute to its	8 - Discover success stories demonstrating digital applications for NEB community	8 - High - there is a lack of common European space that include best practices and	6- Success stories and best practices can be of inspiration but not always easy to	8

SG#2 Appeal → Asset ↓	Relevance of the proposition	Direct advantage (what's in it for me?)	Uniqueness	Ease of exploitation	Overall effectiveness (on a scale 1 to 10, average of the 4 indicators)
	population		success stories that be adopted by industries	replicate	
Elearning catalogue	7 - Attractiveness of the e-learning offer depends on each professional's skills and background	9- learning opportunities, getting recognition via certification, upskilling, visibility if involved as speakers to show best practices	7 - Medium-high (both courses from existing capacity building material and newly developed)	10 - hands-on engaging courses, learning material is provided to all trainees	8.25
Thematic Working Groups (TWGs)	7- selected members of SG#2 with proven experience can join the TWG workshops but all can contribute to suggest online discussion topics in line with the theme of each WG	8 -it provides: -SG#2 visibility, if contributor to state of the art mapping, - access to landscape analysis, - understanding of own role in the industry and potential for partnerships and collaborations	6 - Medium - existing local living spaces environments have experts involved in working groups. However, few of them connect the industrial, digital and NEB worlds.	7- TWG outcomes will feed recommendations report and policy briefs, which may take time to be actually implemented	7
Early Adopters (EAs) network	10 - All SG#2 professionals can become EAs	7 - By becoming EAs, all SG#2 can receive visibility and promote digital solutions they adopt	9 - High - the Early Adopters programme follows the principles of engagement envisioned by the NEB Champions network in terms of digitalisation	5 - Complex and depending on notoriety of NEB at local level	7.75
Roadmap	7 - selected members of SG#2 with strong experience and understanding of NEB world can contribute to roadmap, but wider number of members can provide feedback and suggestions	7 - visibility if contributor to roadmapping, understanding of priorities, strategic insights	10 - High - the Roadmap can provide innovative insights and timings on how to increase the adoption of digital solutions in the industrial sector	6 - Implementation connected to policy context complexity and uncertainty may arise due to the long-term nature of the roadmap	7.5

Table 3 - Articulation of the value proposition for SG#2

3.3. SG#3 - Research and Academia

This SG includes researchers and academicians, as well as European Public-Private Partnerships and project consortia. This SG is eager to find new stimuli for research and publications. However, these players may **lack** full contact with the business community and market players in the NEB and digital domains. They could have problems in understanding or testing the suitability and impact of their research on industry players or lack specific skills or resources on topics that are often essential in

research projects, for instance related to standardisation efforts and outputs, key digital technologies or domain specific knowledge in fields such as architecture, planning and design.

The **benefits** brought by digiNEB.eu to this SG include the possibility to showcase their research results, improve their exploitability and assess interest from the market. It also provides an opportunity to establish collaborations with other researchers, academic institutions and industry representatives, as well as the possibility to get visibility and recognition of their expertise at events or training.

The **main message** to express their specific value proposition would be:

“Find new stimuli for your research, boost your collaborations and partnerships with other researchers but also with industry representatives. Receive feedback from the market on your results and showcase your success stories. Learn from other best practices and share your knowledge educating the next generation of leaders in NEB and digital domains.”

The overall effectiveness of each Asset for this specific SG is indicated in the table below.

SG#3 Appeal → Asset ↓	Relevance of the proposition	Direct advantage (what's in it for me?)	Uniqueness	Ease of exploitation	Overall effectiveness (on a scale 1 to 10, average of the 4 indicators)
Digital Toolkit	7- This asset may be interesting if the SG member has developed a digital solution to showcase	8- SG#3 can discover digital solutions applicable to the NEB domain and showcase their own solution	7 - The toolkit is an additional channel to provide visibility to the solution potentially developed by the SG member	5 - Showcased solutions are meant to be adopted by industry professionals and may require deeper interaction with the developers to understand if they can be upgraded and exploited in a research setting	6.75
Observatory	10 - All SG#3 members can access the Observatory or contribute to its population	10 - Discover success stories and best practices and showcase your own	9 - High - there is a lack of common European space that include best practices and success stories developed by R&I initiatives	8- Success stories and best practices can provide learning opportunity and ideas for synergies	9.25
eLearning catalogue	10- Trainings are relevant for researchers that can act as both instructors and attendants in case they want to master new skills	9- Opportunities to include the catalogue of courses in the curricula and trainings provided by schools and research institutions, opportunities to train or get trained	7- Medium- High: the courses displayed in the eLearning platform are coming from existing material courses or newly developed by the project's partners	10 - hands-on engaging courses whose material can be re-used for own research and training purposes, extensive network of European schools and professional representative bodies contributing to knowledge	9

SG#3 Appeal → Asset ↓	Relevance of the proposition	Direct advantage (what's in it for me?)	Uniqueness	Ease of exploitation	Overall effectiveness (on a scale 1 to 10, average of the 4 indicators)
				sharing	
Thematic Working Groups (TWGs)	7- selected members of SG#3 with proven experience can join the TWG workshops but all can contribute to suggest online discussion topics in line with the theme of each TWG	8- it provides visibility if SG#3 members contribute to state of the art mapping, landscape analysis and help understand gaps for future research	9 - High - By joining the TWGs, SG#3 can create a direct connection with industrial and digital players and contribute to relevant discussion on how research can help increase the adoption of digital solutions	8- TWG outcomes shows gap analysis that can provide research stimuli to bridge such gaps	8
Early Adopters (EAs) network	10 - All SG#3 members can become EAs	7 - Visibility - By becoming EAs, all SG#3 can receive visibility and promote innovative digital solutions they have contributed to develop	10 - High - the Early Adopters programme follows the principles of engagement envisioned by the NEB Champions network in terms of digitalisation	5 - Complex and depending on notoriety of NEB at local level	8
Roadmap	7 - selected members of SG#3 with strong experience and understanding of NEB world can contribute to roadmap, but wider number of members can provide feedback and suggestions	7 - it provides visibility if SG#3 members are contributors to roadmapping, understanding of priorities and strategic insights	10 - High - the Roadmap can provide innovative insights and priorities on how new R&I fundings should be allocated	7- Roadmap can help early detection of future research needs or promising research ideas	7.75

Table 4 - Articulation of the value proposition for SG#3

3.4. SG#4 Digital tech companies and related ecosystem

This SG includes digital technology companies and associations. This SG provides a wealth of digital solutions and tools which may be useful to the purposes of NEB. However, members of this SG may **lack** contact with potential users of their solutions in the NEB environment or find **challenges** in understanding the NEB community's needs.

The **benefits** brought by digiNEB.eu to this SG include a direct link with NEB actors with consequent better understanding of their needs. Also, they have the possibility to engage in a unique ecosystem of research and industrial players that may help solve any possible technical challenge faced in the development of additional solutions as well as provide feedback and support for testing of solutions. Finally, they can get visibility for their digital expertise.

The **main message** to express their specific value proposition would be:

“Find a new market for your solutions, supporting the uptake of digital tools and services relevant for the NEB initiative, understand your users’ better and find partnership opportunities to better prepare your organisation to develop new digital solutions and services.”

The overall effectiveness of each Asset for this specific SG is indicated in the table below.

SG#4 Appeal → Asset ↓	Relevance of the proposition	Direct advantage (what’s in it for me?)	Uniqueness	Ease of exploitation	Overall effectiveness (on a scale 1 to 10, average of the 4 indicators)
Digital Toolkit	10- This asset is primarily dedicated to digital tools developers, as it enables matchmaking with the demand side	10- Showcase your digital solutions and find new users	8 - The toolkit is an additional channel to provide visibility to the solutions developed	7 - providers can find complementary solutions and establish contacts with other providers to co-develop further services	8.75
Observatory	10 - All SG#4 members can access the Observatory or contribute to its population	10 - Discover success stories and best practices and showcase your own use cases	9 - High - The Observatory provides a common space to learn about best practices and success stories in adopting digitalisation in NEB contexts	8- Success stories and best practices can provide learning opportunity and ideas for synergies	9.25
Elearning catalogue	7- digital providers can be involved as instructors to showcase and train about the use of their solutions	8- support the understanding and increase adoption of your tools	7 - Medium -High: the courses displayed in the eLearning platform are coming from existing material courses or newly developed by the project’s partners	8 - collect feedback from users that can be exploited to generate ideas on how to improve your products and services	7.5
Thematic Working Groups (TWGs)	6-only a limited number of providers may be involved in the TWG workshops based on specific needs, but they can contribute to the animation of the online discussion forum	7- understanding of user needs and main trends in specific NEB domains	6 - existing local living spaces environments have experts involved in working groups. However, few of them connect the industrial, digital and NEB worlds	8- TWG outcomes shows gap analysis that can provide room for new ideas and business opportunities	6.75
Early Adopters (EAs) network	1 - This network is dedicated to users, not developers of digital solutions	5 - Indirect visibility via adopters of own solution	6 - Medium - The EAs programme follows the principles of the NEB Champions network. The SG#4 can indirectly benefit from the uniqueness brought by this programme	6 - Possibility to attract new adopters via the ones acting as ambassadors	4.5

SG#4 Appeal → Asset ↓	Relevance of the proposition	Direct advantage (what's in it for me?)	Uniqueness	Ease of exploitation	Overall effectiveness (on a scale 1 to 10, average of the 4 indicators)
Roadmap	7 - selected members of SG#4 with strong experience and understanding of NEB world can contribute to roadmap, but wider number of members can provide feedback and suggestions	7 - visibility if contributor to roadmapping, understanding of priorities, strategic insights	10 - High - the Roadmap can provide innovative insights and priorities on how to increase the adoption of digital solutions in the industrial and research sector	7- Roadmap can help early detection of business needs or promising technological trends	7.75

Table 5 - Articulation of the value proposition for SG#4

3.5. SG#5 Policy Makers

This SG includes policy makers who need continuous feedback and insights to effectively shape their policies at the intersection between the NEB, the digital ecosystem and the Green Deal. This SG may **lack** information about the needs of this variety of players and the barriers existing to the deployment of NEB initiatives. The **benefits** brought by digiNEB.eu is to provide such contact, feedback and insights from the community to fit this SG's policy needs and agenda. The **main message** to express their specific value proposition would be: "Get novel insights to strategically define instruments, actions and policies at the intersection between NEB actors and digital players in support of the future deployment of NEB initiatives".

The overall effectiveness of each Asset for this specific SG is indicated in the table below.

SG#5 Appeal → Asset ↓	Relevance of the proposition	Direct advantage (what's in it for me?)	Uniqueness	Ease of exploitation	Overall effectiveness (on a scale 1 to 10, average of the 4 indicators)
Digital Toolkit	3- This asset is primarily dedicated to digital tools developers and users	6- Get an overview of currently existing digital tools relevant for various NEB domains	6 - Medium - Policy Makers can access the Digital Toolkit to discover available digital solutions applicable in the NEB ecosystem	6 - Understand key technologies to invest in	5.25
Observatory	7- SG#5 members can read the relevant updates in the Observatory	7 - Understand the impact of digital solutions on NEB, learn from use cases and concrete applications	9 - High - SG#5 can find a unique European space to learn more about existing success stories in applying digitalisation for NEB	8- Success stories and best practices can provide key messages and learning points for future policy interventions	7.75
Elearning catalogue	6- This asset is primarily dedicated to digital tools developers and users and NEB actors. However	7- influence content of key trainings	8 - High - the eLearning platform represent a valid tool to lower knowledge skills	8 - produced courses can be re-used in other programmes or developed in synergies with	7.25

SG#5 Appeal → Asset ↓	Relevance of the proposition	Direct advantage (what's in it for me?)	Uniqueness	Ease of exploitation	Overall effectiveness (on a scale 1 to 10, average of the 4 indicators)
	policy makers can contribute to the identification of key topics to include in trainings			other training initiatives such as the NEB Academy	
Thematic Working Groups (TWGs)	8- the outputs of the the TWG analysis provide key insight for policy making	9- landscape analysis and gap analysis will lead to policy briefs with recommendations	10 - High - The TWGs recommendations help shape the digiNEB.eu roadmap	7- TWG recommendations and policy briefs may take time to be actually implemented	8.5
Early Adopters (EAs) network	1 - This network is dedicated to users, not policy makers	7 -Have an overview of adoption rate across Europe	8 - High - Get an overview of Early Adopters programme, useful to get in contact directly with users of digital solutions in the NEB ecosystem	7 - Understanding low adoption areas and define interventions to support adoption	5.75
Roadmap	10 - The roadmap is an essential input for policy making	10 - understand key priorities, strategic insights, investment needs, research ideas	10 - High - The Roadmap provides innovative recommendation and timings of implementation to increase the adoption of digitalisation for NEB	8- Roadmap provides valuable insights but actual implementation may be hindered by policy context complexity and uncertainty	9.5

Table 6 - Articulation of the value proposition for SG#5

3.6. SG#6 National and regional authorities

This SG is composed of National & regional authorities, mayors (including urban planners) and cities. This SG may be aware of local needs, dynamics and characteristics but miss a clear picture of the status of other areas and of the potentialities for collaborations and synergies. Moreover, they may miss the skills and competencies needed to improve liveability in the territory or to concretely develop initiatives at the local level.

The **benefits** brought by digiNEB.eu are to provide a learning environment to acquire new skills, learn from best practices, understand main trends and find networking and partnership opportunities.

The **main message** to express their specific value proposition would be:

“Improve your skills in the digital domain, improve your city’s livability, develop concrete initiatives at the local level and understand the impact of digital and NEB for local communities”.

The overall effectiveness of each Asset for this specific SG is indicated in the table below.

SG#6 Appeal → Asset ↓	Relevance of the proposition	Direct advantage (what's in it for me?)	Uniqueness	Ease of exploitation	Overall effectiveness (on a scale 1 to 10, average of the 4 indicators)
Digital Toolkit	10- All SG#6 members can access the toolkit or contribute to its population	7- Discover useful solutions to improve the livability in your territory	6 - Medium, the toolkit collects existing tools and solutions	7- Most solutions are freely available, but may require some trainings (based on the SG experience) or licences (depending on IPR) to be fully exploited	7.5
Observatory	10 - All SG#6 members can access the Observatory or contribute to its population	8 - Understand and learn from best practices	8 - High - Unique point of access of success stories and best practices	6- Success stories and best practices can be dependent on the context and not easy to replicate in a different territory	8
Elearning catalogue	7 - Attractiveness of the e-learning offer depends on SG member's skills and background	9 - learning opportunities, getting recognition via certification, upskilling	7 - Medium-high (both courses from existing capacity building material and newly developed)	10 - hands-on engaging courses, learning material is provided to all trainees	8.25
Thematic Working Groups (TWGs)	6-only a limited number of SG#6 members may be involved in the TWG workshops based on specific needs, but they can contribute to the animation of the online discussion forum	7- understanding of main trends in specific NEB domains	10 - High - The TWGs recommendations help shape the digiNEB.eu roadmap, useful to provide guidance on how to exploit digitalisation in local contexts	8- TWG outcomes will feed recommendations report and policy briefs, which may provide useful insight for policy making at local level	7.75
Early Adopters (EAs) network	8 - SG#6 can help identify EAs in their local territory	7 - Indirect visibility for the local territory thanks to the recognition provided to the local EAs	10 - High - The EAs can bring best practices to implemented locally	5 - Complex and depending on notoriety of NEB at local level	7.5
Roadmap	8 - The roadmap is a very important input for policy making at local level	10 - understand key priorities, strategic insights, investment needs, research ideas, specific needs at local level	10 - High - The Roadmap provides innovative recommendation and timings of implementation to increase the adoption of digitalisation for NEB in local contexts	8- Roadmap provides valuable insights but actual Implementation may be hindered by policy context complexity and uncertainty	9

Table 7 - Articulation of the value proposition for SG#6

3.7. SG#7 Civil society organisations and citizens

This SG includes civil society organisations, citizens, general public and the society at large. This SG has currently **low awareness** about NEB and how this movement can affect their daily life, thanks to its values of sustainability, inclusion and aesthetics encouraging the green transition. Getting in touch with the project, the SG can understand the benefits and opportunities that can be generated from the development of NEB in their local environment. These include value added services for citizens in areas like health, mobility and living spaces.

The **benefits** brought by digiNEB.eu is to provide information on NEB initiatives and impact, and create opportunities for co-development and active participation.

The **main message** to express their specific value proposition would be:

“Learn about NEB and the adoption of its core values to improve your daily life with greater sustainability, inclusiveness and attention to aesthetics. Access innovative digital solutions that can foster creativity and experimentation in NEB-inspired initiatives to explore new ideas and approaches”.

The overall effectiveness of each Asset for this specific SG is indicated in the table below.

SG#7 Appeal → Asset ↓	Relevance of the proposition	Direct advantage (what's in it for me?)	Uniqueness	Ease of exploitation	Overall effectiveness (on a scale 1 to 10, average of the 4 indicators)
Digital Toolkit	3 - This asset is primarily dedicated to digital tools developers and users	6- Get an overview of currently existing digital tools relevant for various NEB domains	6 - Medium - SG#7 can access a platform to scout existing digital solutions that they can adopt to improve the quality of their lives.	5 - While some digital tools could potentially be adopted by citizens, they represent a subset of available solutions	5
Observatory	7- SG#7 members can read the relevant updates in the Observatory	7 - Understand the impact of digital solutions and NEB in local communities	9 - High - SG#7 can understand, through the success stories, how digitalisation has improved the lives of citizens in European cities	8- Success stories and best practices can provide key messages and learning points to guide citizens' behaviours	7.75
Elearning catalogue	6- This asset is primarily dedicated to digital tools developers and users and NEB actors. However interested users can also join and improve their knowledge and skills	7 - learning opportunities, getting recognition via certification, upskilling	8 - High - SG#7 can get access to available learning courses to increase the adoption of digital solutions	8 - hands-on engaging courses, learning material is provided to all trainees	7.25
Thematic Working Groups (TWGs)	4- The outputs of the TWG analysis provide key insights, crucial to be implemented to	6- landscape analysis and gap analysis can provide insights on the impact of NEB and digitalisation	8- High - The TWGs outputs represent an innovative element for SG#7 to better understand policy	6- TWG recommendations and policy briefs may take time to be actually implemented and	6

SG#7 Appeal → Asset ↓	Relevance of the proposition	Direct advantage (what's in it for me?)	Uniqueness	Ease of exploitation	Overall effectiveness (on a scale 1 to 10, average of the 4 indicators)
	improve citizen's wellbeings	on citizen's life	priorities that affect their daily life	have an impact on the society at large	
Early Adopters (EAs) network	8- Potentially all members of SG#7 are eligible to become EAs	7 - By becoming SG#7 can receive visibility and promote innovative digital solutions they have adopted	10 - High - SG#7 can be in contact with other Early Adopters and better understand how they have adopted digital solutions in the NEB ecosystem	5 - Complex and depending on notoriety of NEB at local level	7.5
Roadmap	5- interested SG#7 members can provide feedback and suggestions to the roadmap via consultations	7 - understanding of priorities, strategic insights, possible impact on cities and possible roles of citizens	10 - High - The Roadmap provides innovative recommendations and timings of implementation to increase the adoption of digitalisation for NEB to improve citizens' quality of life	6 - Implementation connected to policy context complexity and uncertainty may arise due to the long-term nature of the roadmap	7

Table 8 - Articulation of the value proposition for SG#7

4. Communication and dissemination plan

Given the strategy described in Sec. 2 and throughout the 24-month duration of the project, all project partners have commitments and effort to contribute to community development and stakeholder engagement on a continuous basis as part of the project's dissemination and communication plan. The exploitation element, drafted in Sec. 5 "Exploitation strategy", addresses the commitment of the digiNEB.eu consortium partners beyond the project lifetime.

The dissemination and communication plan includes activities that focus on reaching further afield, in particular focussing on the economic, societal and environmental benefits that NEB-related technologies and solutions can bring to society as a whole and potential adopter. With the definition and exploration of the R&I landscape, market needs and scenarios, and adoption stories, digiNEB.eu will continuously package information from best practices emerging from use cases, best practices and testimonials. The overall plan aims to:

1. Create an active network which facilitates engagement and cooperation between NEB stakeholders;
2. Analyse innovation in the NEB landscape including requirements, barriers to adoption and gaps;
3. Map NEB-related projects and identification of the assets displayed in the NEB Digital Observatory;
4. Promote digital solutions and services to be adopted by the NEB Early Adopters community in the Digital Toolkit of R&I results and services;
5. Provide multi-stakeholder engagement and synergy opportunities through events and groups such as the EAG and TWGs;
6. Capacity building and best practice sharing through an online eLearning platform and materials.

4.1. digiNEB.eu Communication & Engagement Campaigns

In executing the communication and dissemination plan, digiNEB.eu takes a campaign approach with specific, targeted and measured activities that directly support project goals.

The campaigns will support four distinct phases of the project to provide efficient and effective resources management and engagement with the stakeholders.

The 4 phases are:

- **DEVELOP (M01 - M106):** this phase involves creating the core message, identifying the target audience, and defining the campaign's objectives. The goal is to develop clear and concise messages that resonates with the intended audience and motivates them to take action;
- **ENGAGE (M07 - M12):** In this phase, the campaign is launched and promoted through various channels and programmes to generate interest and engagement with the target audience;
- **VALIDATE (M13 - M18):** In this phase, the effectiveness of the programme launched in the previous phases by transferring best practices;
- **EMBED (M18 - M24):** This phase involves integrating the campaign message into the organisation's overall communication strategy to ensure consistency and continuity.

As visible in the Figure below, each phase is supported by communication activities, which are explained in more detail in the next sections.

Figure 2 - Campaigns phases and channels utilised

The campaigns are built on series of elements:

- Content rich posts, placing project results in the wider NEB and DG CONNECT landscape;
- Visual and digiNEB.eu branded elements, to build a strong visual identity for the NEB initiative;
- A user-centric approach, showcasing user experiences and stories to communicate the digiNEB.eu the value proposition for each of the identified stakeholder groups.

4.2. Campaign #1: Branding, Project Communication and Awareness

This campaign is focused on increasing relevant stakeholders’ awareness of the project by communicating, with a consistent visual identity, the project’s key assets, addressed challenges, activities, outputs and expected impacts via project’s communication channels. Chapter 4 presents the plan for each activity showcased in Table 7, which include the creation of branding materials, the launch of the project’s website, the set up of social media channels, the publication of press releases, newspieces and articles, as well as the implementation of PPC campaigns.

This campaign is essential to establish digiNEB.eu’s identity and presence among the New European Bauhaus environment and its stakeholders. Given the scope of this campaign, its activities started from M01 (October 2022). The Table below showcases the main goals, activities, results, and targeted stakeholders involved in this campaign.

Duration / Phase	Goals	Activities	Main results (as of M06)	Stakeholder Groups
From October 2022 to September 2023 (Develop and Engage phases)	Develop a visual identity to make the project recognisable as part of the New European Bauhaus community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Development of branding materials (graphic templates, newsletter, roll-up banner, bookmarks) -Launch of the digiNEB.eu branded website -Set up of social media channels -Press release launch and promotion -Pay-Per-Click Campaigns -Newspieces and articles about the project’s goals on the website and social media channels 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Website visits: 7212 -Number of videos recorded: 11 -Video recording views: 1043 - Communication channels set-up (LinkedIn, Twitter, Instagram, YouTube) -Post-webinar reports: 1 -Social media followers: 598 -Number of PPC: 1 	All stakeholders

Table 9 - Campaign 1 - characteristics and main results

4.3. Campaign #2: Showcasing and sharing digital solutions for NEB

This campaign aims to showcase the innovation brought by digital solutions for the New European Bauhaus, from technological and social points of view, to all identified stakeholder groups. The campaign #2 includes the launch of the NEB Digital Ecosystem, which is composed of the Digital Toolkit, Observatory (which also includes TWG interactive discussions) and the eLearning Platform. As already presented in the deliverable D2.1 “digiNEB.eu web platform, Rel. 1.0”.

The start of this campaign was proved by the launch of the Digital Toolkit in October 2022, which was followed by the Observatory in November 2022. The last component of the digital ecosystem is planned for March 2023 with the eLearning platform.

The main goals, activities, results, and targeted stakeholders involved in Campaign #2 are showcased in the Table below.

Duration	Goals	Activities	Main results (as of M06)	Stakeholder Groups
From October 2022 to September 2023 (Develop and Engage phases)	Showcase the benefits brought by digitalisation in the NEB environment, thanks to the development of the NEB digital ecosystem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Launch of the Digital Toolkit, Observatory and eLearning platform on the digiNEB.eu website -Mapping of digital solutions to be displayed in the Digital Toolkit and presented as success stories in the Observatory -Mapping of eLearning courses to be added to the related platform -Set up of TWG discussions accessible through the Observatory 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Digital solutions added to the Digital Toolkit: 67 -Success stories in the Observatory: 16 -Mapped eLearning courses: 6 -Number of TWG discussion groups: 4 	All stakeholders

Table 10 - Campaign 2 - characteristics and main results

4.4. Campaign #3: Recruitment to webinars, workshops, annual and 3rd-party events

The aim of this campaign is to maximise the SGs participation to digiNEB.eu webinars, workshops and annual events to learn more and contribute to increase the adoption of digital solutions in the NEB ecosystem. On the other side, in order to showcase the benefits brought by the project, the digiNEB.eu project members aim also to join 3rd-party events.

Given the CSA nature of this project, the project team has organised and joined events from its launch. The full list of planned activities has been presented in D4.1 “Stakeholder engagement plan and adoption monitoring report 1.0”.

Tactics to bring into life this campaign include seamless registration and event follow-up on website; tailored social media campaigns (bannered promotion across multiple channels; branded hashtags, live tweeting/polling, media cards with speaker image/graphics); newsletters; professional multimedia content and Pay-Per-Click campaigns.

The main goals, activities, results, and targeted stakeholders involved in Campaign #3 are showcased in the Table below.

Duration	Goals	Activities	Main results (as of M06)	Stakeholder Groups
From October 2022 to September 2024 (Develop,	Recruit members of all identified SGs through events, to	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Organisation of 8 webinars -Organisation of 16 workshops -Organisation of 2 annual events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Webinars organisation: 2 -Workshops organisation: 2 	All stakeholders

Duration	Goals	Activities	Main results (as of M06)	Stakeholder Groups
Engage, Validate and Embed phases)	showcase the benefits of applying digital solutions in the NEB ecosystem and increase their adoption	-Participation to 3rd-party events -Newsletter preparations -Promotional materials and banners to promote events -Social media activities to promote events -Pay-Per-Click Campaigns to identify and recruit new experts	-3rd-party events attendance: 10 -Newsletters preparation: 4 -Graphic materials to promote events (both on social media and website): 20+ -Number of PPC campaigns: 1	

Table 11 - Campaign 3 - characteristics and main results

4.5. Campaign #4: Early Adopters engagement

Campaign #4 aims to recruit digiNEB.eu Early Adopters. As stated in D3.1, an Early Adopter is a stakeholder who has actively and positively engaged with digital strategies for NEB projects, Smart Communities or NEB-aligned initiatives. An Early Adopter is distinct from a ‘user’ in that they are likely to encourage and promote the use of these strategies amongst colleagues and peers, as well as provide feedback and contribute expert knowledge that may lead to improvements in the systems implemented. The Early Adopters will act as ambassadors of digiNEB.eu, and as a consequence, promote the adoption of digitalisation in NEB environments. The digital solutions promoted by Early Adopters will be boosted as success stories in the Observatory and in the Digital Toolkit. Moreover, if there is an interest, Early Adopters can also become members of the Thematic Working Groups.

As this campaign is going to be after the submission of this deliverable, the activities to be performed define the strategy to be followed to recruit the Early Adopters. The main results also showcase the means by which the effectiveness of the campaign is going to be evaluated.

Duration	Goals	Activities	Main results	Stakeholder Groups
From April 2023 to April 2024 (Engage and Validate phases)	Recruit and engage with architects, designers, engineers, researchers, and industrial players that have direct experience using digital tools aligned with the NEB principles.	-Set up of the registration form on the digiNEB.eu website to make the application to the programme -Recruitment of Early Adopters through social media channels, newsletters, DEM -Early Adopters Press Release -Early Adopters success stories -Early Adopters’ solutions in the Digital Toolkit -Organisation of events with the Early Adopters	-Number of Early Adopters applications received -Number of Early Adopters recruited -Number of events joined by Early Adopters -Number of digital solutions adopted by the Early Adopters	SG #1, SG #2, SG #3, SG #4

Table 12 - Campaign 4 - characteristics and main results

4.6. Campaign #5: Policy Recommendations

This campaign aims to deliver influential recommendations within dedicated policy briefs, landscape and gap analysis, and a strategic Roadmap to influence future work programmes in the NEB and digital environments. The reports are prepared by the digiNEB.eu team in cooperation with members of the

Thematic Working Groups and External Advisory Board members, providing, therefore, recommendations in the areas of:

- Design and Architecture
- Production and Construction
- Community and Sustainability
- Education

As for the previous campaign, this one is going to run after the submission of this deliverable, the activities to be performed (and presented in the Table below) define the strategy to be followed to develop policy recommendations. The reported main results showcase the means by which the effectiveness of the campaign is going to be evaluated.

Duration	Goals	Activities	Main results	Stakeholder Groups
From April 2023 to September 2024 (Engage, Validate and Embed phases)	Develop policy briefs, landscape and gap analysis, and a strategic Roadmap to influence future work programmes in the NEB and digital environments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Recruitment of TWGs through the digiNEB.eu network or through Early Adopters applications -Policy recommendations Press Release -Digital solutions identified by TWGs added to the Digital Toolkit -Organisation of workshops with the TWGs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Policy briefs produced by TWGs -Landscape and gap analysis produced by TWGs -Release of the digiNEB.eu Roadmap -Number of workshops with the TWGs 	SG #5, SG #6

Table 13 - Campaign 5 - characteristics and main results

4.7. Campaign #6: Support to exploitation and sustainability

This last campaign aims to communicate the main impact gathered through the exploitation activities of the project.

The campaign takes place in the last stage of the project lifetime and is strongly connected to Campaign nr. 5, due to the fact that all the recommendations reported in the landscape and gap analysis reports and in the digiNEB.eu Roadmap help define the future directions the digital ecosystem for NEB needs to take to make the building and local living spaces environments more beautiful, sustainable and inclusive.

As for the campaign “Policy Recommendations”, this one is going to take place after the submission of this deliverable. The activities to be performed (and presented in the Table below) define the strategy to be followed to develop an exploitation and sustainability strategy. The reported main results showcase the means by which the effectiveness of the campaign is going to be evaluated.

Duration	Goals	Activities	Main results	Stakeholder Groups
From April 2024 to September 2024 (Embed phase)	Communicate the main impact gathered through	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Final project’s policy event -1st annual event to showcase the preliminary results of the TWGs landscape and gap analysis reports and of the digiNEB.eu Roadmap 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Monitoring KERs impact -White paper to showcase the impact of digitalisation and 	All stakeholders

Duration	Goals	Activities	Main results	Stakeholder Groups
	exploitation activities	-2nd annual event to showcase the final results of the TWGs landscape and gap analysis reports and of the digiNEB.eu Roadmap	recommendations coming from the TWGs -Number of attendees to the annual events	

Table 14 – Campaign 6 - characteristics and main results

4.8. Cross-campaign Digital Marketing & Communication channels and elements

In order to implement the dissemination and communication campaigns, the digiNEB.eu team is going to utilise channels and elements, as showcased in the Table below.

Channels refer to all means used to exchange information about the project’s main outputs. The elements, on the other side, are the activities that can be used in the channel to communicate and disseminate the messages.

The following sections present in more details the channels and elements used to build the communication and dissemination strategy.

4.8.1. Website

The project website is the central channel to perform dissemination and communication activities. As already presented in D2.1 “digiNEB.eu web platform, Rel. 1.0” the website is continuously evolving its UX (User Experience) along with the evolution of the NEB initiative, as well as the feedback provided by the end-users and the various consortium partners. The prime strength of the website from a communication and dissemination point of view lies in the technical content it delivers to the digiNEB.eu stakeholders (e.g. success stories, discussions in the TWGs). Such a content, complemented by communication actions, and adequately optimised for SEO purposes, will lead to the expected increase of end-users, hence digiNEB.eu community members. The website serves also as a repository of trustworthy sources of information linked to the project achievements: an accessible gateway where each user can find the main project’s assets and interact with other players, including:

- **Press Releases:** press releases are a written communication element in a journalistic style to inform the digiNEB.eu SGs about the main outcomes of the project. The Press Releases are published under the News section on the website.
- **Newspieces and Articles:** they report useful information on the progress of the project and main achievements. They are included in the News section of the website.
- **White papers:** they are developed to provide in-depth information and analysis on topics discussed by TWGs. They are going to be published in a dedicated section, “Publications”, on the digiNEB.eu website
- **Landscape and Gap reports:** both reports are going to be developed in cooperation with TWGs and EAG. Landscape reports provide a comprehensive view of the current state of the level of digitalisation in NEB, while gap reports are to identify areas where digitalisation needs to be further adopted. Both reports are going to be included in the TWGs sections of the website.
- **Policy Briefs:** they are a concise document that presents key information and recommendations on how to increase the adoption of digital solutions for NEB. They are going to be published in the TWGs sections of the website.
- **Banners and infographics:** Banners are graphic products used to mainly promote events. Infographics are visual representations of information and data, that include charts, graphs

and other visual elements to present complex information. They are both developed to promote events and highlight their main outcomes.

- **Public project deliverables:** These documents will be uploaded after formal approval from the EC.

4.8.2. Videos

The videos created by digiNEB.eu are available in two main categories: video interviews in short, easily digestible segments featuring project partners discussing the main objectives of digiNEB.eu, and other informative videos highlighting the project's significant achievements. Additionally, the project records live events, making them available to a wider audience through its YouTube channel, which can be accessed from the homepage of the project website.

4.8.3. Newsletters

Newsletters are an essential tool for keeping stakeholders informed and up-to-date on the project's main activities, thereby increasing visibility and awareness of the project's objectives. digiNEB.eu publishes monthly newsletters (called "News Digests") that cover a range of topics related to the project's work. The newsletter content focuses on promoting digiNEB.eu events, presenting the NEB Digital Toolkit and NEB Observatory success stories, highlighting the eLearning platform, promoting the Early Adopters programme launch, and encouraging participation in TWGs discussions. All newsletters are available in a dedicated section on the project website ([here](#)), providing easy access to past and current issues. By distributing newsletters, digiNEB.eu ensures that stakeholders are kept informed of the project's progress, developments, and achievements. Through this regular communication, the project team can foster engagement and interest from stakeholders and keep them up-to-date on the latest developments, thereby building a strong community around the project's work.

4.8.4. Social media

The social media channels are an instant form of communication with community members and potentially interested people or organisations who would like to engage with the digiNEB.eu consortium. Social media channels help ensure continual visibility of the project's efforts to targeted stakeholders like webinars, workshops or general events and announcements. The overall design and promotion of communication and dissemination activities is strengthened through:

- **Twitter:** digiNEB.eu leverages on this widespread social media channel to share instantaneous updates and promote upcoming project activities, such as the launch of the Digital Toolkit, Observatory, eLearning platform, TWGs and Early Adopters programme.

Consistently posting tweets is part of the weekly social media presence activities and will be crucial to sustain brand awareness, drive website traffic, and generate leads. For this reason, the digiNEB.eu team posts at least once a week and has generated almost 20K impressions in the first 6 months of activities. The posts that have gained the most traction are those promoting videos and events.

Examples of Twitter posts of digiNEB.eu are shown in the Figure below. The approach has already been proved to be successful, as the results (see also Sec. 6 "Monitoring") indicate direct relation with content-rich tweets and increase of the community.

Figure 3 - Sample of posts on Twitter

LinkedIn: digiNEB.eu actively utilises LinkedIn as a key platform for reaching a wide audience of architects, designers, engineers, professionals in the construction industry, SMEs and companies operating in the digital domain, researchers and academicians, policymakers, and other stakeholders interested in our project. By creating and regularly updating a dedicated LinkedIn page, the consortium shares project updates, relevant news, events, and success stories with our network. Furthermore, LinkedIn is used to create 1-to-1 connections and scout experts to join the digiNEB.eu activities or exploit one of the assets built by the project, such as the Digital Toolkit, Observatory, eLearning platform, TWGs and Early Adopters programme. digiNEB.eu strategically engages with other relevant groups and pages on LinkedIn, expanding its reach and fostering collaboration across various sectors. By leveraging LinkedIn's vast user base, digiNEB.eu not only raises awareness about the digital ecosystem of the New European Bauhaus, but also facilitates meaningful dialogues, knowledge exchange, and the building of relationships that may lead to future synergies and opportunities for collaboration. The use of LinkedIn as a dissemination channel is instrumental in ensuring our project's impact on a European and global scale.

LinkedIn posts are published once per week and have generated almost 16K impressions in the first six months. Examples of LinkedIn posts are shown in the Figure below.

Figure 4 - Sample of posts on LinkedIn

- **Instagram:** the digiNEB.eu Instagram presence is designed to capture the attention of artists and the general public, highlighting how the project can boost the implementation of digital solutions in the New European Bauhaus. To achieve this goal, the project team develops visually appealing graphics, stories, and reels that present the main results in a creative and

visually appealing way, foster a sense of community and promote engagement and participation. The figure below showcases examples of our Instagram posts, which are produced weekly with a coverage of over 500 unique accounts.

Figure 5 - Sample of posts on Instagram

- YouTube:** YouTube is the world’s most used video-sharing platform, counting more than 2 billion monthly active users /4/. Trust-IT has a positive previous experience on YouTube with similar EC-funded initiatives and therefore digiNEB.eu will be present on this social media for videos. YouTube also provides us with powerful analytics tools for better understanding video performance. Within the project, YouTube serves as the primary platform for uploading, storing, and sharing webinars, videos and other audio-visual materials. During the project’s first semester, digiNEB.eu uploaded 10 videos on YouTube, which received a total of 1043 views.

Figure 6 - YouTube homepage

The main achievements gained in terms of community engaged through social media channels are reported in Sec. 6.

4.8.5. Email

Email is a very useful channel to drive:

- **Email marketing campaigns**, which are going to be used to recruit new members to join the Early Adopters programme, TWG discussion groups, decrease their knowledge gap by applying to the eLearning courses and/ or present digital solutions in the Digital Toolkit and their adoption as a success story;
- **Newsletters**, which are going to convey the same messages included in the DEM, but also graphic elements and images in the messages.

4.8.6. Workshops

Sixteen workshops will be delivered by digiNEB.eu. They will be one of the central ways to convey effective comms & dissemination messages, both before and after their taking place. Before in terms of generating awareness and participation around some of the topics discussed and after in order to generate further engagement, leveraging on the technical content produced at the event. This facilitates a multi-stakeholder dialogue and creates opportunities for the EAG, TWG members and digiNEB.eu's network to exchange ideas and solutions. Workshops are held as F2F events, hybrid models or fully online.

Furthermore, with workshops, the digiNEB.eu communication team is going to support engagement with the development of roll-up banners, branded materials and/ or videos.

Figure 7 - Roll-up banner and sample of branded materials

However, when the workshop is organised in a hybrid or fully online mode, the team aims to use additional tools to engage the community, such as mentimeter or sli.do.

The full list of workshops organised by the team and engagement strategies is available in D4.1 “Stakeholder engagement plan and adoption monitoring report 1.0”.

4.8.7. Webinars

Webinars are online seminars or presentations that allow the participants to better understand the goals of building a digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus.

Webinars provide a platform to the digiNEB.eu assets, the EAG members, the Early Adopters and provide discussion around the work and results of the TWGs. The webinars will also identify commonly perceived barriers and to discuss how different R&I projects are addressing them. The webinars will form a core aspect identifying how current activities can shape the future and contribute to roadmapping and policy recommendations.

Figure 8 - Graphic materials and some screenshots from the webinars

More details about the engagement strategy developed through webinars is provided in D4.1 “Stakeholder engagement plan and adoption monitoring report 1.0”.

4.8.8. 3rd-party events

Third party events are organised and executed by external partners from the digiNEB.eu consortium. They span from conferences to panel discussions and help digiNEB.eu gain visibility, communicate benefits for target audiences, gain insights into the latest digital innovations to support the NEB community and make new contacts as part of the community development.

In order to make presentations more compelling, the digiNEB.eu partners prepare graphic materials (e.g. powerpoint presentations, banners, fliers) to be showcased during the event.

Figure 9 - Some screenshots from digiNEB.eu's partners at 3rd-party events

The full list of 3rd-party events attended by the team is available in D4.1 “Stakeholder engagement plan and adoption monitoring report 1.0”

4.8.9. Pay-Per-Click Campaigns

The PPC campaign is a type of online advertising in which the advertisers pay each time a user clicks on one of their ads by selecting specific keywords. They are typically displayed on search engine results pages and can be an effective way for businesses to reach a targeted audience and drive traffic to their website.

For digiNEB.eu, the PPC campaigns are prepared to increase project awareness, reach and recruit Early Adopters, as well as encourage participation in TWG discussions and visits to the NEB digital platform.

To ensure successful campaigns, the digiNEB.eu team will conduct keywords analysis using the keyword planner of Google Ads. Examples of keywords that are going to be used are New European Bauhaus, digitalisation, technology, sustainable building, urban planning, and the PPC campaign will be adjusted based on their performance.

The campaigns are focused on Europe, as the New European Bauhaus movement is based in this geographic area. The team utilises Google's Search and Display campaigns to increase website traffic, and Video campaigns to encourage engagement and views on YouTube.

Each campaign runs for a limited period of time, approximately two weeks.

By following this strategy, digiNEB.eu can effectively reach and engage with their target audience and promote the project objectives.

In M03, digiNEB.eu ran a video PPC campaign on YouTube to increase awareness of the project's main goals. The campaign sponsored the video "[digiNEB.eu in one word](#)," which gained 14.6K impressions. In the coming months until the end of the project, the digiNEB.eu team aims to run at least two more campaigns to further increase awareness of the project's main assets.

4.9. Role of multipliers

In the context of communication and dissemination campaigns, multipliers play a crucial role in amplifying messages and extending their reach beyond the immediate target audience. Multipliers are individuals, organisations, or channels that possess significant influence and credibility within their respective communities, and are capable of leveraging their social capital to disseminate information and generate interest. Multipliers can act as intermediaries between the campaign and its intended audience, creating a bridge that helps to overcome barriers to communication and trust. As such, they can play a critical role in building momentum and social proof around the campaign, thereby strengthening its credibility and legitimacy and providing it with a means to extend their reach and credibility beyond their immediate target audience.

By detecting and partnering with multipliers since its early inception, digiNEB.eu's communication and dissemination campaign significantly increased the visibility, impact, and effectiveness of its messaging. Leveraging the power of social networks and online communities, the project's multipliers could reach large audiences and drive engagement and participation.

- **Architects, Designers, Engineers (SG1):** Multipliers in this group include professional associations, trade publications, and influential actors within the architecture/design/engineering landscape. Partnering with these multipliers means to reach a specialised audience and build credibility within the professional community, in order to ensure greater adoption and uptake of digiNEB.eu solutions and practices.
- **Industry Players (SG2):** Multipliers in this group include business leaders and industry analysts. By partnering with these multipliers, digiNEB.eu's communication and dissemination campaign could generate interest and momentum around the solutions' innovation potential, eventually leading to increased adoption and market penetration.
- **Research and Academia (SG3):** Multipliers in this group include scholars and academics and respected scientific publications. By partnering with these multipliers, the project's

communication and dissemination campaign aims to increase the visibility and impact of research findings, leading to greater uptake and adoption of new knowledge and insights.

- **Digital Technology Companies (SG4):** Multipliers in this group include prominent tech companies and technology adopters. By partnering with these multipliers, digiNEB.eu aims to leverage their reach and influence to generate interest and adoption of new technologies and digital tools.
- **Policy Makers (SG5):** Multipliers in this group include international political organisations, advocacy groups, and policy think tanks. By partnering with these multipliers, digiNEB.eu aims to generate support and momentum for landscape analysis and policy proposals, leading to increased advocacy and adoption in the EU political context.
- **National & Regional Authorities (SG6):** Multipliers in this group include influential politicians and community leaders at both regional and national levels. By partnering with these multipliers, the project's communication and dissemination campaign aims to generate support and awareness for initiatives and policies, leading to greater buy-in and engagement from regional and national authorities.
- **Civil Society Organizations and Citizens (SG7):** Multipliers in this group include community organisers, NGOs, and respected media outlets. By partnering with these multipliers, digiNEB.eu aims to generate interest and engagement among citizens, leading to greater awareness and adoption of social and environmental initiatives.

So far, all groups have been approached and involved in the digiNEB.eu community's initiatives through a multi-channel engagement strategy. An updated table of multipliers was already published in D4.1 "Stakeholder engagement plan and adoption monitoring report 1.0" dealing with synergies. For further data about multipliers engagement and their participation in digiNEB.eu various initiatives see Section 6.3.

4.10. Role of synergies

Establishing strong synergies with players in the NEB and built environments to foster the adoption of digital solutions is one of the main pillars of digiNEB.eu. Through collaboration activities the project aims to foster the adoption of digital solutions to make living spaces more inclusive, sustainable and beautiful.

Starting from the launch of the project, digiNEB.eu has started to cooperate with relevant initiatives involved in both NEB and digital environments, as already presented in D4.1 "Stakeholder engagement plan and adoption monitoring report 1.0".

The main categories of initiatives digiNEB.eu has engaged with are:

- **NEB Lighthouse Projects:** demonstrators that can showcase how to create more sustainable, inclusive, and beautiful spaces in locations across Europe while involving communities to achieve green transition locally;
- **digiNEB.eu sister CSA projects:** projects funded under digital Europe programmes that share common goals of digiNEB.eu, such as the sharing of benefits of adopting digital solutions to make living spaces more sustainable;
- **NEB-oriented and sustainable living spaces projects and initiatives:** EU-funded projects or initiatives aimed at building more sustainable, inclusive and beautiful living spaces.

The Table below presents an update on the type of synergies established and cooperation mechanisms put in place.

#	Initiative name	Type of initiative	Initiative's main objectives	Website link	Type of cooperation
1	CULTUURCAMPUS	NEB Lighthouse project	Cultuurcampus aims to transform the disadvantaged urban area of Rotterdam South (NL) into a sustainable hub of arts, research, learning and community as a catalyst. The project achieves this objective by blending education, research, policy, and culture and considering the lived experiences of its residents.	https://www.cultuurencampusrotterdam.nl/en/	The project team is going to be engaged through dedicated workshops where they can bring their own experiences in Rotterdam to help implement the NEB principles thanks to digitalisation. In addition, CULTUURCAMPUS is going to be added as a success story in the Observatory and the digital solutions exploited by the project in the Digital Toolkit. Whereas possible, experts from this group are going to be recruited to join TWG and become Early Adopters.
2	NEB-STAR	NEB Lighthouse project	NEB-STAR showcases how territorial transformation plans can incorporate the principles and values of the NEB in Stavanger (NO), Prague (CZ) and Utrecht (NL). The project tackles four emblematic challenges linked to climate-neutral cities, all considering local needs and concerns through co-creation with residents and stakeholders.	https://nebstar.eu/	The NEB-STAR team is going to be engaged through dedicated workshops where they can bring their own experiences in Norway, Czech Republic and the Netherlands to make them climate-neutral environments thanks to the use of digital solutions. NEB-STAR is going to be added as a success story in the Observatory and the digital solutions exploited by the project in the Digital Toolkit. Whereas possible, experts from this group are going to be recruited to join TWG and become Early Adopters.
3	NEBourhoods	NEB Lighthouse project	NEBourhoods prepares Munich-Neuperlach (DE) for the future as mapped out by the European Green Deal regarding the built environment, circularity, mobility, energy, food, and health. The project will build on the area's strengths – a strong sense of	https://www.nebourhoods.de/	NEBourhoods team members are going to potentially join one of the digiNEB.eu TWG and join dedicated workshops where they can bring their own experiences in Munich to make the construction sector more sustainable.

#	Initiative name	Type of initiative	Initiative's main objectives	Website link	Type of cooperation
			community, vast green areas, and large-scale housing, even if in need of renovation – and address its weaknesses – higher than average unemployment and lower than average education levels.		NEBourhoods is going to be added as a success story in the Observatory and the digital solutions exploited by the project in the Digital Toolkit. Whereas possible, experts from this group are going to be recruited to join TWG and become Early Adopters.
4	DESIRE	NEB Lighthouse project	The project aims to tackle the major challenges faced by societies and cities: climate change, biodiversity loss and resource challenges. Based on three main themes of inclusivity, circularity and reconciling cities with nature, DESIRE will use art, architecture, and design to explore alternative ways of transforming territories across different European cities in Denmark, the Netherlands, Italy, Latvia and Slovenia.	https://www.irresistiblecircularcociety.eu/	DESIRE and digiNEB.eu are going to exploit their best practices to make living spaces more sustainable, beautiful and inclusive by joining workshops and co-organised events. The DESIRE team members might be willing to join one of the digiNEB.eu TWG.
5	EHHUR	NEB Lighthouse project	EHHUR supports cities and vulnerable residents in transforming their built environment. Spread across seven different locations in the EU and Associated Countries (Denmark, Belgium, Portugal, Italy, Greece, Turkey, and Croatia), it will seek to tackle socioeconomic and cultural challenges such as social segregation, energy poverty, and degradation of depopulated historical centres.	https://eyesheartshands.eu/	EHHUR is going to provide best practices on how to transform the build environment into a more sustainable one by following NEB principles. Best practices of how digital solutions have helped this process can be added into the NEB Digital Toolkit and as success stories in the Observatory. Moreover, members of EHHUR might be willing to join the digiNEB.eu TWG.
6	Bauhaus of the Seas	NEB Lighthouse project	The project aims to promote renewed ethical and aesthetic regenerative development from a diverse range of dimensions of our continued relationship with the sea. Conceived as a journey with Portugal as a starting point, the Bauhaus of the Seas will generate a design movement extending to all European coastal and maritime regions.	https://bauhaus-seas.eu/	All the digital solutions adopted by Bauhaus of the Seas are going to be included as best practices in the Observatory and the Digital Toolkit. Moreover, both projects plan to join co-organised workshops and webinars to exchange best practices.
7	DS4SSCC	Sister project	Data Space for Smart and Sustainable Cities and Communities is an EU-funded initiative that prepares for the creation of a data space for smart	https://www.ds4sscc.eu/	DS4SSCC and digiNEB.eu have established a communication task force (together with living-in.eu and Goli.eu) where the

#	Initiative name	Type of initiative	Initiative's main objectives	Website link	Type of cooperation
			communities as an enabler of the EU Green Deal goals and Sustainable Development Goals		coordinators of the initiatives meet monthly to discuss synergies and cooperation activities. The projects cooperate by co-organising workshops and events and helping in dissemination and communication activities. Moreover, the digital solution developed by DS4SSCC is planned to be included in the Digital Toolkit and Observatory.
8	Living-in.eu	Sister project	Through co-creation with citizens, the project aims to bring the economic and social benefits of this transformation to all local communities and implement an inclusive digital Europe with powerful digital services, technologies, infrastructures and skills)	https://living-in.eu/	Living-in.eu and digiNEB.eu have established a communication task force (together with DS4SSCC and Go Li.eu) where the coordinators of the initiatives meet monthly to discuss synergies and cooperation activities. The projects cooperate by co-organising workshops and events and helping in dissemination and communication activities. Living-in.eu is planned to be showcased as a success story in the Observatory.
9	Go Li.eu	Sister project	The Go Li.eu project will support and accelerate the European way of digital transformation by coordinating and further enhancing strong multi-level governance cooperation in the EU to develop, (re-)use and share trustworthy solutions, technology and standards. To make this possible Go Li.EU will ensure effective governance and growth of the Living-in.EU community, to include all ecosystem players, ensuring cooperation among them and with other EU initiatives.	N/A	Go Li.eu and digiNEB.eu have established a communication task force (together with DS4SSCC and Living-in.eu) where the coordinators of the initiatives meet monthly to discuss synergies and cooperation activities. The projects cooperate by co-organising workshops and events and helping in dissemination and communication activities.

#	Initiative name	Type of initiative	Initiative's main objectives	Website link	Type of cooperation
10	CrAft	NEB-oriented and sustainable living spaces project	Creating Actionable Futures (CrAft) is part of the New European Bauhaus (NEB) supports the Mission Board on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities and the NetZeroCities platform in designing and deploying Climate City Contracts, based on knowledge from CrAft's 3 Sandbox Cities (Bologna, Prague, and Amsterdam) and 60 CrAft Reference Cities.	https://craft-cities.eu/	CrAft and digiNEB.eu are going to cooperate together through the HRB programme as they have been included in the same project group. The cooperation between the two projects spans from organising events to sharing digital solutions that will be added to the Digital Toolkit of success stories in the Observatory.
11	Auroral	NEB-oriented and sustainable living spaces project	AURORAL focuses on increasing connectivity and delivering a digital environment of smart objects interoperable services platforms able to trigger dynamic rural ecosystems of innovation chains, applications and services.	https://www.auroral.eu/#/	The cooperation between the two projects spans from organising events to sharing digital solutions that will be added to the Digital Toolkit of success stories in the Observatory.
12	MatchUp	NEB-oriented and sustainable living spaces project	MATCHUP is a EU-funded Smart City project involving three lighthouse cities and four follower cities. MATCHUP cities will join forces to reshape their social, economic and environmental models and to promote social inclusion, liveability and prosperity for their citizens.	https://www.matchup-project.eu/	The cooperation between the two projects spans from organising events to sharing digital solutions that will be added to the Digital Toolkit of success stories in the Observatory.
13	The Hut	NEB-oriented and sustainable living spaces project	The Hut aims to build a safe space to cope with climate extremes. The project involves 10 areas around Europe where new ways to limit/manage risks associated with climate change will be tested.	https://thehut-nexus.eu/	The cooperation between the two projects spans from organising events to sharing digital solutions that will be added to the Digital Toolkit of success stories in the Observatory.

#	Initiative name	Type of initiative	Initiative's main objectives	Website link	Type of cooperation
14	New European Bauhaus Friendship Group	NEB-oriented and sustainable living spaces initiative	The initiative teams up with inspiring networks, associations, and organisations committed to acting as promoters and key interlocutors throughout the New European Bauhaus initiative.	https://new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/about/friends_en	The cooperation with this initiative helps digiNEB.eu to join engagement programmes strategically aligned with NEB core communities.
15	NEB Goes South	NEB-oriented and sustainable living spaces initiative	NEB Goes South is a NEB Lab, a co-creation space at the service of the New European Bauhaus community, for the delivery of beautiful, sustainable, and inclusive projects to improve our daily lives. The project connects six south European countries which join forces to reflect about and improve education through architecture	https://new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/get-inspired/inspiring-projects-and-ideas/neb-lab-neb-goes-south_en	The cooperation with this initiative helps digiNEB.eu to join engagement programmes strategically aligned with NEB core communities.
16	New European Bauhaus of the Mountains	NEB-oriented and sustainable living spaces initiative	The NEB of the Mountains is a way of thinking, living, exploring – bringing together physically, but also virtually different stakeholders dealing with and mountain topics. The aim is to implement the New European Bauhaus initiative on a regional level, in South Tyrol.	http://mountainbauhaus.eu/	The cooperation with this initiative helps digiNEB.eu to join engagement programmes strategically aligned with NEB core communities.
17	Nordic Carbon Neutral Bauhaus	NEB-oriented and sustainable living spaces initiative	This community-led NEB Lab project is an open forum for the discussion of how architecture, design and art can help in achieving a carbon neutral and inclusive way of building and living.	https://new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/get-inspired/inspiring-projects-and-ideas/neb-lab-nordic-carbon-neutral-bauhaus_en	The cooperation with this initiative helps digiNEB.eu to join engagement programmes strategically aligned with NEB core communities.

#	Initiative name	Type of initiative	Initiative's main objectives	Website link	Type of cooperation
18	NEB Stewardship Lab	NEB-oriented and sustainable living spaces project	In the NEB Stewardship Lab, the project team aims to explore and enhance the role of higher education in the NEB initiative. The project co-develops the NEB Stewardship model to make the initiative more accessible and tangible for higher education institutions and students.	https://www.metropolia.fi/en/about-us/news-and-events/neb-stewardship-lab-launch	The outcomes and best practices developed by the NEB Stewardship Lab can be integrated as part of courses in the eLearning platform.
19	InnoRenew	NEB-oriented and sustainable living spaces initiative	InnoRenew CoE is an independent research institute established in 2017 through the InnoRenew project. Its research targets renewable materials and sustainable buildings, specifically innovative approaches to wood and its use, with the goal of transferring scientific knowledge into industrial practice.	https://innorenew.eu/	InnoRenew representatives have been invited to join events organised by digiNEB.eu. Moreover, as InnoRenew is involved in shaping the NEB Academy, part of the courses developed by them can be integrated in the eLearning platform.
20	UserCentriCities	NEB-oriented and sustainable living spaces project	UserCentriCities is a platform for local authorities to compare their performance with their peers and exchange mutual learning about how to deliver user-centric services.	https://www.usercentricities.eu/	The cooperation between the two projects is focused on sharing digital solutions that will be added to the Digital Toolkit of success stories in the Observatory.
21	Horizon Results Booster (HRB)	EU-funded project	EU-funded initiative that provides guidance to create a results portfolio and execute common dissemination strategy for a cluster of projects.	https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu/	While HRB is not a NEB focused initiative, digiNEB.eu has been included in a cluster group where NEB projects have been included, such as CrAFt and the Lighthouse projects.

Table 15 – Established synergies by M06

Figure 10 below summarises the synergies established by the digiNEB.eu team in the first six months from its launch.

Figure 10 – Types of established synergies

The timely implementation of the campaigns is showcased in Figure 11 “Timeline for dissemination and communication activities and related campaigns”.

In addition, since the very beginning of the project, the digiNEB.eu team has established a cooperation with the **NEB Communication team** to ensure that the project’s dissemination, communication and exploitation plan is aligned with the New European Bauhaus initiative. This joint effort helps guarantee that the designed campaigns promote specific objectives and achievements of digiNEB.eu, while advocating the overarching goals of the NEB community. The digiNEB.eu and NEB Communication team members involved in this task force are presented in the Table below.

Name	Team	Role
Celia Dejon	NEB Communication Team	NEB media main point of contact
Adalbert Jahnz	NEB Communication Team	European Commission's spokesperson's service
Rita Giuffrida	digiNEB.eu project	digiNEB.eu WP5 Leader
Claudio de Majo	digiNEB.eu project	digiNEB.eu Task 5.1 Leader
Maria Giuffrida	digiNEB.eu project	digiNEB.eu Technical Deputy Coordinator

Table 16 – digiNEB.eu and NEB Comms Team Task Force

Figure 11 - Timeline for dissemination and communication activities and related campaigns

5. Exploitation Strategy

This section establishes the main pathways of exploitation for the partners of digiNEB.eu, both individually and collectively (or as small groups), leveraging the results, competences, and experience gained during the project lifetime.

This is an initial version of the exploitation strategy, as the final version of this section will be developed during the project lifetime and will be published in the final release of this document, due in Month 24 (September 2024).

5.1. Key Exploitable Results (KERs)

As mentioned in section 3.1.2.2 of digiNEB.eu’s Grant Agreement, one of the goals of this deliverable also is to define a series of campaigns that will run throughout the digiNEB.eu project to disseminate and support exploitation of its main Key Exploitable Results (KERs).

5.1.1. Horizon Results Platform

A Key Exploitable Result (KER) is an identified main interesting result which has been selected and prioritised due to its high potential to be "exploited" – meaning to make use and derive benefits - downstream the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research or education. All the KERs showcased in the previous section are going to be published on the [Horizon Results Platform](#) by the end of the project.

The Horizon Results Platform is the online repository set-up by the European Commission as a *tool for exploitation of results and assets coming out of European funded projects*.

The opportunity of publishing the KERs on this platform is to make them openly available to all interested stakeholders and get in contact directly with them.

5.1.2. digiNEB’s KERs after the first semester of activities

The table below summarises digiNEB.eu’s KERs as of April 2023 (M07) and their specific pathway to impact creation.

KER	Impact pathway
KER#1. NEB Observatory	The NEB observatory was set up in M02 and it the “centre of gravity” of digiNEB.eu’s dissemination means, as it continuously presents, in a dynamic way, the latest and most relevant outcomes of the “NEB digitalisation effort”, including success stories linked to digital solutions, novelties from the discussion forums (digiNEB.eu’s TWGs), recent events and news linked to the digiNEB.eu context, etc. User interaction and feedback plays a relevant role in the priority logic with which the Observatory presents in time the various elements.
KER#2. NEB Digital Toolkit	The NEB Toolkit, launched in M01, provides resources, services and tools to support digitalisation of the NEB community. All solutions of the Toolkit are accurately selected and publicly available for free consultation.
KER#3. eLearning catalogue and platform	The platform has been launched in M07 and features training courses to support the NEB community. The courses in the catalogue are going to be either hosted in the eLearning platform (at the end of which they will receive a digiNEB.eu certification) or they are going to be external resources, about which trainees are informed by digiNEB.eu, before being specifically directed to them, supporting their training path.
KER#4. TWGs (Collaborative Space)	The TWGs support and facilitate information sharing and competence building for the whole NEB community, with a specific focus on the role of digital technologies. This will happen also by means of open consultations, findings validation, and dissemination activities. The TWGs will be the main, authoritative way to establish digiNEB.eu as a

KER	Impact pathway
	content-rich platform. Moreover, after sufficient content is available on the TWGs, recommendations on digitalisation gaps in the EU context will be produced and disseminated through all possible channels.
KER#5. digiNEB.eu community database	The digiNEB.eu community database is hosted on the collaborative, Drupal-based website. The community will be nurtured and presented with all opportunities that will be gathered by digiNEB.eu.
KER#6. digiNEB.eu event format(s)	digiNEB.eu’s Workshops, Webinars, and Yearly Events are proving to be an effective and synergistic way of supporting NEB. The events format is being evolved considering firstly feedback from the audience, and including sustainability considerations. With 20+ events in the planning, more evidence on the exploitation leverage of the digiNEB.eu events format will be gathered in the coming 6 to 12 months. The first yearly event will take place in Q4/2023 and the 2nd one towards the end of the project (September 2024).
KER#7. Network of digiNEB.eu Early Adopters	The Early Adopters will act as Ambassadors of digiNEB.eu, at local and pan-European level, receiving in return visibility and international recognition for their efforts.

Table 17 - KERs and impact

The ambition of the digiNEB.eu Consortium is to consolidate the aforementioned KERs and to further expand them according to the upcoming plans indicated in digiNEB.eu’s Grant Agreement.

5.2. Individual exploitation

Each digiNEB.eu partner is planning to autonomously build on the 24-month experience guaranteed by the Project and their initial model and means of exploitation after project completion are briefly indicated in the table below. All individual exploitation plans will be revised as the project unfolds. A final version of the plan and specific opportunities sought for will be prepared in Month 24 of the project (September 2024).

Partner	Pillars of the individual exploitation plan	Specific knowledge and opportunities developed with digiNEB.eu
TU DELFT	TU Delft will continue advocating for the importance of digital ecosystems for the built environment and the green transition. Also by continuing to contribute to the New European Bauhaus through the lighthouse projects. TUD will continue looking for opportunities to offer academic expertise to support the EC in the great challenges of our time.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Digital solutions that can be used by students and researchers ● Network of relevant actors in the built environment developing digital tools ● Connecting institutions in the construction sector
Trust-IT + COMMpla	Trust-IT will exploit its expertise gained in the specific, rapidly developing domain of NEB to be involved in more initiatives in this area, including locally funded. Moreover, Trust-IT and its affiliated entity COMMpla will pursue the opportunities of supporting synergistic initiatives and members of the digiNEB.eu community with digital communication and marketing services and solutions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Thematic domains and running initiatives ● Opportunities in the NEB Academy development ● Domain knowledge in the NEB context

Partner	Pillars of the individual exploitation plan	Specific knowledge and opportunities developed with digiNEB.eu
ICF	ICF will continue to promote and develop the novel paradigms emanating from the junction of Smart Communities and New European Bauhaus Principles, and transferring those to the future EU Digital Agenda. ICF will also pursue novel research directions that have resulted from the combination of the ICT research knowledge and NEB community grassroots and bottom-up approaches to generating new knowledge.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Novel research directions ● New methods for place-based and grassroots engagement with digital technologies ● Inclusive, accessible, sustainable models in education and curricula
EAAE	The EAAE will keep spreading knowledge and expertise gained during the project throughout its network of Architecture Schools. Also, the EAAE will keep focusing on the various ways (including digital) through which NEB connects with built environment education and research. The main goal is to reach out to the future generation of professionals - the students of today.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Digital solutions in the framework of NEB connecting to designers communities ● Enhancing interdisciplinary approaches towards the use of NEB principles ● Pointing out new opportunities and innovative pathways
IW	<p>IW will continue to develop the synergies generate by the project and provide guidance and knowledge to implement education, innovation, and relevant technologies, that have a positive impact on the quality of life in the society as well as on the sustainability of the wood industries.</p> <p>InnovaWood will enlarge its network and collaborations with the NEB community, promoting more visibility of wood industrial innovation and research for the green transformation of the built environment.</p>	<p>digiNEB.eu results, best practices and partnerships can feed into:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Open Innovation Platform: together with other RTOs, IW is launching a new OIP for innovative products and building systems including digital. ● NEB Academy: IW's members include leading higher education institutions which can benefit and contribute to the NEB Academy. ● Wood4Bauhaus: IW's policy alliance will further foster awareness around biobased, renewable building solutions and digital innovations within NEB and the construction sector. ● Follow-up EU projects: IW is supporting various new consortia of members, who are increasingly adopting the NEB values and principles in the project design.

Table 18 - Individual exploitation plans

Notwithstanding their legitimate objective of individual exploitation, the Partners agree to perform every reasonable effort to achieve an agreement for one or more joint exploitation streams.

5.3. Joint exploitation strategy

The joint exploitation strategy will be developed once the project KERs will be consolidated and sufficient feedback from the various stakeholder groups is collected. The strategy will indicated what the partners are going to exploit together after project completion, leveraging on the assets (built on the KERs) the project will leave behind.

The path that will be followed as part of the digiNEB.eu workplan is the following:

1. Definition of the **exploitation model and exploitation strategy** for each of the KERs or groups of KERs (aka “assets”).
2. Preparation of the **exploitation agreement(s)** amongst the relevant partners.
3. Insertion of the exploitation agreement(s) as annexes to the final **exploitation plan**.

An initial building block of the to-be joint exploitation strategy of digiNEB.eu is reported in the table below, which provides a practical example of the analytical process that will be followed to achieve the best possible exploitation plan that maximises digiNEB.eu’s impact.

digiNEB.eu KER	Possible exploitation model	Partners interested	Strategy
KER#1. Observatory	Sponsorship model for construction industry players	Trust-IT, ...	Animate the observatory and collect sponsors. Best practices free to be published.
KER#2. Digital Toolkit	Sponsorship model for ICT solution providers	Trust-IT, ...	Sustain the Toolkit as the go-to catalogue for engineers and architects operating in the NEB context and attract providers for visibility on the toolkit, without taking sides for any particular ICT solution
KER#3. eLearning catalogue and platform	Partnerships with training institutions	EAAE, ...	Maintain the momentum for architecture schools, institutions and companies to contribute to the elearning platform.
KER#4. TWGs	TBD
KER#5. digiNEB.eu community database	Central point for NEB community to share and exploit digital-led solutions.	...	Continued implementation and financing of database through follow-up EU projects under NEB umbrella.
KER#6. digiNEB.eu events format	TBD
KER7. network of digiNEB.eu Early Adopters	TBD
...more?	TBD

Table 19 - Elements at the basis of the joint exploitation plan

The preliminary table reported above is in a draft version and will be finalised in the next 6 to 12 months, leading the way to initiative from any of the partners concerning joint exploitation of digiNEB’s KERs (foreground knowledge).

5.4. Road ahead and draft plan

In the remaining 17 months of the project, both the individual exploitation plans and the joint exploitation strategy and plan of digiNEB.eu will be completed. The plan is to sign the exploitation

agreement(s) mentioned in Sec. 5.3 above and ultimately deliver an actionable and measurable exploitation plan.

5.4.1. Strategic digiNEB.eu Roadmap

Based on recommendations from TWGs and events (particularly, workshops), the roadmap that will be developed by digiNEB.eu addresses gaps and/or issues that prevent the development of digital solutions for NEB and will chart a course for future deployment. The roadmap represents a key outcome to inform policy measures both in a European and National perspective and as such it will also identify main pathways for exploitation within and outside the digiNEB.eu Consortium.

The following communication and outreach activities here below will contribute to generate insights for policy making:

- The project will facilitate a continuous dialogue with the NEB community supported by the EAG, the TWGs and the workshop and events, which will lead to 4 Policy Briefs summarising findings, observations, and recommendations for key decision-makers.
- The project will liaise with National initiatives and Member States to map and identify synergies between different local actors to produce policy developments and digital upskilling.
- The project will solicit input from the various stakeholder communities and valorise them appropriately through a set of core communication activities and engagement mechanisms (as described in D4.1).

All of these inputs will pave the way for the production of Deliverable D5.2 “NEB Digital Deployment roadmap” containing a strategy for the adoption of NEB values (sustainability, inclusiveness, and aesthetics) based on lessons learned, best practices and actionable recommendations coming directly from the various communities to help orient future initiatives.

6. Monitoring

The impact assessments of strategically important digiNEB.eu activities are based on a core set of key performance indicators (KPIs), which are used wherever they can be quantified. This allows digiNEB.eu to track the effectiveness of its activities and make data-driven decisions to improve outcomes. As already remarked in D4.1, as the task leader for T4.3 Trust-IT shares the results of these monitoring activities with all partners, ensuring that everyone involved in the project is informed and able to contribute to its success.

6.1. KPI dashboard

Qualitative metrics come into play whenever there is a need for a deeper analysis of the relevance of outcomes achieved. To tangibly monitor the impact of the digiNEB.eu activities, an online dashboard will be created by M06 and continuously updated, including all relevant KPIs mapped by the digiNEB.eu project. At present (M06), many KPIs related to digiNEB.eu’s dissemination, communication and exploitation activities are already trackable and appear in line with the M24 objectives. The table below monitors the DECP KPIs results table first approved in digiNEB.eu Grant Agreement (table 12) versus end-of-project expectations. Some of these KPIs also appeared in the project’s general KPIs table presented in D4.1 at M03 (Table 7).

KPI#	Description	Status at M06	Target (M24)
1	Digital solutions mapped and part of the digiNEB.eu Toolkit	67	250
2	Marketing Campaigns (involving press creation, Social media announcement, Graphic material, Infographics etc.)	3	6
3	Members of the NEB Digital Early Adopters (formerly known as Champions) Network	2	100+
4	Newsletters (sent out)	4	21
5	Number of European NEB projects/initiatives mapped and part of the digiNEB.eu Observatory	16	500
6	Number of validated/authenticated users engaged through the outreach events (webinars + workshops + yearly events)	302	2000
7	Original videos produced and published	10	24
8	Policy briefs by TWGs	N/A (available from Sept 2023)	4
9	Social media content items published on social media (Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram)	229	192
10	Social media followers (total all channels)	598	7000
11	Synergies created	21	100
12	Trainees	N/A (eLearning platform will be released by M06)	1000
13	Unique visitors to digineb.eu (cumulative)	7212	50000
14	User database spanning all relevant stakeholder (incl. social media)	1149	3000
15	Visualisation of videos (cumulative)	1043	120000
16	Webinars organised (100 attendees each)	2	8
17	Workshops organised (50 attendees each)	2	16
18	Yearly events organised (150 attendees each)	N/A (1st one in Sept 2023)	2

Table 20 – KPI dashboard

6.2. Google analytics

As already pointed out in D4.1, digiNEB.eu’s website analytical data has been gathered continuously using Google Analytics and is still being monitored weekly using a custom Google Data Studio dashboard to derive detailed statistics about online engagement.

The Google Analytics profile was set up in M1, and the first data about traffic sources, visitors, navigation paths and conversions are being tracked. The profile allows to monitor the **traffic KPI** (Traffic: # sessions per month >1.5k at M12, >5k at M24) carried out in conjunction with WP4. Other relevant metrics include such as **individual logins, session duration, number and frequency of new vs returning users, conversion actions** (e.g., submitting a web form or downloading a pdf) and breakdown dimensions such as **traffic sources, visitor geographies, most viewed pages**, etc. The combination of these activities has helped monitor and achieve the communication target KPI listed above, helping the communication teams focus on activities that are not only designed to increase traffic but also ensure social media visits.

This DECP discloses primary data dynamic engagement strategies will respond to real-time online metrics, displaying project update reports as a more statistically significant data source. A customised dashboard depicting our Google Analytics results has been set up to monitor these breakdown dimensions and will be updated monthly until M24 (September 2024). As it can be appreciated in the snapshot below, traffic has been experiencing a steep growth thanks to upcoming communication and engagement activities.

Figure 12 - digiNEB.eu dashboard - Marketing Website Summary

The dashboard indicates that over the course of the first half-year, the website has accrued a total of 7,299 views, of which 2,885 constitute unique sessions. It should be noted that the number of sessions only includes users who consented to the digiNEB.eu cookie policy, accounting for approximately 40% of the total visitors. To calculate the remaining 60%, a simple formula can be applied: 2,885 multiplied by one divided by 0.4 ($2,885 \times 1/0.4$), which results in a total of 7,212 visitors. Consequently, there were 4,327 visitors who did not accept the cookie policy.

The number of users who visited the website during the aforementioned period is 1,172. Of these users, 30.21% were returning, suggesting a high level of user retention. Additionally, the website demonstrated an average monthly increase of approximately 70% new users, indicating a consistent growth rate.

The aforementioned data, as presented on the dashboard, indicates that the website has been successful in attracting and retaining visitors. Through analysis of this data, it is possible to gain insights into the website's performance and make informed decisions regarding future improvements.

Figure 13 - digiNEB.eu dashboard - Social Media Performance

The social media accounts associated with the website have a combined following of 598 individuals, which comprise 335 LinkedIn connections, 185 Twitter followers, and 78 Instagram followers. Among these platforms, LinkedIn is the most popular and generates the highest levels of engagement. In particular, LinkedIn has registered a greater amount of attention than Twitter or Instagram, with an average engagement rate that surpasses those of the other platforms. This is related to the fact that the digital and industrial communities are mainly present on LinkedIn, which is a professional social media.

Overall, the data reveals that the LinkedIn account is performing the strongest, with a high engagement rate and a notable number of followers. However, there is potential for growth across all social media platforms, and a deeper analysis of the engagement metrics can assist in determining what tactics and content resonate most with the audience to further increase engagement and broaden the reach of the website.

6.3. Community DB

digiNEB.eu's website constitutes the main platform of the community. The website provides various stakeholders, including start-ups/SMEs, policymakers, experts, NGOs, and industry and business actors, with value-added information, services, engagement, and discussion opportunities. It aims to bring together research, industry, and business actors to foster collaboration, through its value-proposition assets. These include the NEB Observatory, the NEB Digital Toolkit, the eLearning Platform with original training material, a series of Thematic Working Groups (TWGs) on relevant topics and vertical conversations, a series of engaging events (including two yearly events, eight webinars and 16 Workshops by M24), and a series of R&I ecosystem landscape and gap analysis exercises leading to policy recommendations.

All community members participating in one of these initiatives have done and will do so through the digiNEB.eu platform by registering and creating a personal account. As specified in D1.2, data collected directly on the digiNEB.eu website are stored on a relational database management system (RDBMS) MySQL. The specific digiNEB.eu implementation includes a customised graphical theme which is stored on the Trust-IT servers and the dataset collected internally, excluding data shared with external services (i.e. YouTube) are stored in Trust-IT servers hosting digineb.eu and located on Amazon AWS Cloud (EC2 instances), in the European region of Ireland.

For the website (www.digineb.eu), the main entry point for the data stored and used by the project, the open framework Drupal (Drupal 9), has been adopted to manage the content of the website. Access to the Drupal databases is limited only from the server machine and the users accessing the data are given dedicated and customised privileges. The source data from any feedback forms undertaken is not made public and only used for the purposes of gathering feedback for platform improvement.

Overall, the digiNEB.eu community accounts for 1149 unique members, representing different SGs with different interests for the project. Presented below is a visual representation illustrating the data related to the digiNEB.eu community. The data analysis encompasses information gathered from a range of stakeholders within the project's community, which includes individuals who are registered on the website (such as creators and users of digital solutions, and proprietors of success stories), as well as followers on various social media platforms (such as Instagram, Twitter, and LinkedIn), and attendees of events (so far only two webinars have been organised).

As observable in the graphic below, the stakeholder categories in digiNEB.eu are fairly evenly represented, with the first four groups ranging from 15 to 22 percent in their representation rates. The most represented group is SG1, which includes architects, designers, and engineers, and makes up over 22 percent of the project's stakeholder community. This is because SG1 has a practical interest in digiNEB.eu's platform and solutions, which can be useful for their daily work. SG2 (industry players) and SG4 (digital technology companies) also have high engagement rates, at over 17 percent and over 15 percent respectively, due to their interest in adopting or developing digital solutions for strategic industrial sectors like construction or wood production. SG3 (research and academia) has an engagement rate of over 20 percent, which can be attributed to the project's goal of producing didactic materials and gap analyses, as well as the fact that two consortium members are academic institutions. SG7 has a relatively high representation rate of over 11 percent, driven by the interest of NGOs in NEB values and the diverse range of other categories represented by the group (civil society, organisations, and citizens). The two groups with lower representation rates, SG5 (policy makers) and SG6 (national & regional authorities), each have a representation rate of about 6 percent, which is due to the fact that the project has not yet included the formulation of policy briefs in its activities. However, as the project develops training programs and thematic working groups, it is expected that the representation of SG5 and SG6 will increase.

Figure 14 – Representation of digiNEB.eu SGs in percentage

The geographical makeup of the digiNEB.eu project closely aligns with its EU-focused identity, which embodies the core values of the New European Bauhaus initiative. As the NEB is a European movement, the majority of stakeholders engaged in the first 6 months are coming from this continent (92%), with Italy, Belgium and Spain as countries most interested in the project’s activities. However, all European countries are proportionally represented, ranging from 7% to 3%. Moreover, apart from Europe, the digiNEB.eu project has also attracted people from all continents, which represents 8% of the overall community.

Figure 15 – digiNEB.eu community country representation in percentage

Figure 16 – digiNEB.eu community continents representation in percentage

7. Conclusion and next steps

This 1st version of the Plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication provides a motivated, commensurate and actionable set of activities that have been and will be carried out to achieve the project objectives, leveraging on the actions and content produced by the other tasks of digiNEB.eu. This plan is developed and agreed-upon as part of WP5 “Outreach, roadmap, and sustainability”, which involves support from all project partners. It defines the strategy for communication, dissemination and exploitation and sets out plans up to project completion.

The main conclusions are:

- The document is to be considered as a living document, enabling partners to update it as needed as part of the coordination of the “Outreach, roadmap and sustainability” work package (WP5) whenever necessary and progressively ahead of the production of the second version due in M24 (September 2024);
- The current version of the plan is tightly linked to the project results, particularly the KERs (see Sec. 5.1);
- It defines the preliminary elements of exploitation and sustainability (see Sec. 5) in relation to policy recommendations captured in the project’s Roadmap;
- The keystone of the document is the overall plan, reported in Sec. 4.5;
- A set of campaigns (see Sec. 4.2) has been planned to concretely and measurably help the digiNEB.eu team to increase awareness towards digital solutions for NEB and support achievement of the project’s KPIs;
- The strong cooperation with the NEB Communication Team, led by the EC, ensures that digiNEB.eu’s dissemination, communication and exploitation is aligned with the New European Bauhaus initiative and focuses on promoting the specific objectives and achievements of digiNEB.eu, with the ultimate goal of increasing the size of the NEB community, at pan-European level and in line with the EC’s expectations.

8. References

/1/ D1.1 ‘Project Handbook’, the digiNEB.eu Consortium, December 2022.

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/3/.D4.1 ‘Stakeholder engagement plan and adoption & monitoring report – initial version’ - the digiNEB.eu Consortium, February 2023.

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